

FEGA Metadata Technical Report

EGA v2 model

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Glossary of Terms and Abbreviations

Abbreviations	Description
ADF	Array Design Format file specification
AF	Array Format
API	Application Programming Interface
BAM	Binary Alignment/Map sequencing file
BioData.pt	Portuguese Infrastructure of Biological Data
BSRC	Biomedical Sciences Research Center
CEGA	Central EGA (EMBL-EBI and CRG).
CGA	Centre for Genomic Analysis
CI	Continuous Integration
CRG	Centre for Genomic Regulation
DAA	Data Access Agreement
DAC	Data Access Committee
DCAT	Data Catalog Vocabulary (W3C standard)
DCAT-AP	Data Catalog Vocabulary Application Profile
DCTERMS	Dublin Core Terms
EGA	European Genome-phenome Archive
EHDS	European Health Data Space
ELSI	Ethical, Legal, and Social Implications
EMBL	European Molecular Biology Laboratory
EMBL-EBI	European Molecular Biology Laboratory – European Bioinformatics Institute
ENA	European Nucleotide Archive
ENVO	Environment Ontology
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
FEGA	Federated EGA
FHD	Federated Human Data
FOAF	Friend of a Friend

Abbreviations	Description
GA4GH	Global Alliance for Genomics and Health
GDI	Genomic Data Infrastructure project
GDI HDM	GDI Harmonized Dataset Model
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GH	GitHub
GHGA	German Human Genome-Phenome Archive
GoE	Genome of Europe
HCA	Human Cell Atlas
HUMANn	HMP Unified Metabolic Analysis Network
IGSR	The International Genome Sample Resource
INSERM	Institut National de la Santé et de la Recherche Médicale
IRI	Internationalized Resource Identifier
ISA	Investigation Study Assay
JGA	Japanese Genotype-phenotype Archive
JSON-LD	JSON for Linked Data
MixS	Minimum Information about any (x) Sequence
MQA	Metadata Quality Assessment
MWG	Metadata Working Group
NAKO	NAKO Gesundheitsstudie, German National Cohort
NBIS	National Bioinformatics Infrastructure Sweden
NGS	Next Generation Sequencing
NU	Norwegian University
OBI	Ontology for Biomedical Investigations
OLS	Ontology Lookup Service
OLS4	Ontology Lookup Service v4
OWL	Web Ontology Language
PEG	Predictor Effector Gene
PRIDE	PRoteomics IDentifications Database

Abbreviations	Description
PROV-O	Provenance Ontology
PSI	Proteomics Standards Initiative
QC	Quality Control
RDF	Resource Description Framework
RDFS	RDF Schema
SDRF	Sample and Data Relationship Format for Proteomics
SEMAPV	Semantic Mapping Vocabulary
SIB	Swiss Institute of Bioinformatics
SKOS	Simple Knowledge Organization System
SPARQL	RDF query language and protocol
UiO	University of Oslo
UL	University of Lodz
URI	Uniform Resource Identifier
UT	University of Tartu
UU	University of Uppsala

Term	Definition
Biomaterial	Biological sample or derivative
Cardinality	The relationships between entities and their instance-level numerical constraints (e.g., many to many, exactly one, etc.)
Catalog	Node-level collection of dataset metadata
Catalog Record	Administrative entry describing one dataset
CEGA	Central EGA, jointly managed by the EMBL-EBI and CRG
Cohort	Group of individuals or samples sharing traits
Continuous Integration	Practice where developers frequently merge changes into a shared repo and each change triggers automated builds and tests to catch issues early
CURIE	Compact URI form <code>prefix:reference</code> that expands via a prefix map to a full IRI. Specified by W3C CURIE Syntax 1.0 ⁴⁴

⁴⁴ <https://www.w3.org/TR/2010/NOTE-curie-20101216/>

Term	Definition
Data Service	Endpoint that serves one or more datasets
Datafile	Digital file containing experimental data
Dataset	Controlled-access bundle of related datafiles
Dataset Series	Thematic collection of separate datasets
EGA v1 Model	The current metadata model (as of January 2026) that has been in production (i.e., in use) since the establishment of the EGA in 2008. It is used until the EGA v2 model is in production by CEQA for submissions, and by FEQA nodes that use the Local EGA ⁴⁵ .
EGA v2 Model	The second major iteration of the EGA metadata model, proposed by the FEQA MWG in this document, and still to be implemented.
Identifier	Stable reference string for an entity
IRI	Like a URI but allows Unicode; can be losslessly converted to a URI by percent-encoding. Defined in RFC 3987 ⁴⁶
JSON Schema	JSON format for validation rules
JSON-LD context	Mapping that converts JSON keys to IRIs
Linked Data	Web of data connected by resolvable IRIs
Metadata	Data that describes other data. For example, "blue" in "a blue pen"; or "diabetes" in "a patient with diabetes"
Ontology	Structured representation of concepts, including controlled vocabulary with defined relations
Policy	When in uppercase, it refers to the entity "Policy" of the EGA v2 model, representing a statement of data-use and access conditions; when in lower case, it refers to the everyday sense of a general organisational rule or practice
Process	Activity representing the execution of a protocol with inputs and outputs
Project	Umbrella grouping of related studies and datasets
Protocol	Step-by-step scientific method description
Protocol Collection	Versioned set of related protocols
Serialisation	Concrete encoding of a data model into a specific file or message format, such as JSON, XML or RDF/Turtle.
SPARQL endpoint	Service that answers SPARQL queries

⁴⁵ <https://github.com/EGA-archive/LocalEGA>

⁴⁶ <https://www.rfc-editor.org/rfc/rfc3987>

Term	Definition
Study	Scientific investigation or analysis bundle
URI	ASCII identifier string for a resource using the generic syntax. Defined in RFC 3986 .
URL	A URI that provides a network location for retrieval (for example <i>https</i>). Defined in RFC 1738 .

1. Executive summary

The **Federated EGA (FEGA) Metadata Working Group (MWG)** has designed a new, **process-oriented metadata model** intended to replace the EGA v1 model⁴⁷, used by Central EGA (CEGA) and FEGA nodes using Local EGA⁴⁸. It prepares the FEGA network for FAIR, linked-data interoperability across **human omics**. **The model is under active development, and this report⁴⁹ accompanies that work in progress.** What exists today is an abstract specification and a first set of JSON Schema drafts⁵⁰ with embedded JSON-LD contexts; detailed serialisations, production deployments and full validator roll-out are future milestones, not completed deliverables.

Core **entities** include Biomaterial, Protocol, Process, Datafile, Dataset, Policy, Data Access Committee (DAC), Study, Cohort, Project, Protocol Collection and DCAT-style Catalog objects. **Validation** through the open-source **ELIXIR Biovalidator**⁵¹ ensures both syntactic and selected semantic checks (e.g., ontology term validation). **Use-case workshops** in genomics, microarrays, proteomics, and microbiomes confirmed the model's flexibility without needing schema rewrites.

A **transparent GitHub repository**⁵² contains the schemas, documentation, versioning, automated workflows, and a change process aligned to FEGA's network governance. As the first stepping stones for **future migration** of the current EGA v1 model to the EGA v2 model, we propose completing the set of model schemas, an initial v1-to-v2 model mapper, and a test implementation at CEGA. Finally, we present a phased adoption by FEGA nodes and other stakeholders. This approach would culminate when the maturity and efficacy of the model have been proved end-to-end and the model shift can happen in the production environments.

Disclaimer(s): *this document is a snapshot of the live documentation of the FEGA MWG as of February 2026. New content and changes will be added to `docs/technical-report.md`⁵³. Some materials referenced in this document are only accessible to members of their respective groups (ELIXIR, GDI and FEGA). To gain access to them, request membership through the official channels.*

⁴⁷ <https://ega-archive.org/submission/metadata/ega-schema>

⁴⁸ <https://github.com/EGA-archive/LocalEGA>

⁴⁹ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18802072>

⁵⁰ <https://github.com/M-casado/fega-metadata-schema/tree/main/schemas>

⁵¹ <https://github.com/elixir-europe/biovalidator>

⁵² <https://github.com/EGA-archive/fega-metadata-schema>

⁵³ <https://github.com/EGA-archive/fega-metadata-schema/blob/main/docs/technical-report.md>

2. Introduction

In the era of rapidly expanding human genomics data in research and healthcare, efficient data reuse is gaining importance to maximise benefits for patients. The 1+Million Genomes (1+MG) Initiative⁵⁴ was launched in 2018 to enable access to one million sequenced human genomes across Europe, and provided a cohesive vision to support diverse jurisdictional data sharing requirements. This has prompted the establishment of federated genomic data sharing networks in Europe, which catalysed the development of multiple projects, including the **Federated European Genome-phenome Archive (FEGA)**^{55,56}.

Since its launch in 2022, the FEGA Network (see [Figure 1](#) and [Figure 2](#)) has become fully operational, coordinated by CEGA, based in EMBL's European Bioinformatics Institute (EMBL-EBI) and the Centre for Genomic Regulation (CRG), and as of January 2026 it consists of **nine national nodes** (Finland, Germany, Norway, Spain, Sweden, Poland, Portugal, Canada, and most recently Switzerland)⁵⁷, and has 53 datasets available⁵⁸.

The complexities, challenges, and achievements of FEGA, unravelling the dynamic interplay between regulatory frameworks, technical challenges, and the shared vision of advancing genomic research to improve global health have recently been described in the FEGA marker paper published in *Nature Genetics*⁵⁹.

⁵⁴ <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/1-million-genomes>

⁵⁵ D'Altri, T., Freeberg, M. A., Curwin, A. J., Alonso, A., Freitas, A. T., Capella-Gutierrez, S., ... & Keane, T. M. (2025). The Federated European Genome–Phenome Archive as a global network for sharing human genomics data. *Nature Genetics*, 1-5.

⁵⁶ <https://ega-archive.org/about/projects-and-funders/federated-ega>

⁵⁷ <https://ega-archive.org/about/projects-and-funders/federated-ega>

⁵⁸ https://ega-archive.org/search/federated_ega.*?type=dataset

⁵⁹ <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41588-025-02101-9>

Figure 1. Overview of the FEAGA network and the workflow of data provenance and access requests.

Figure 2. Federated EGA network overview, highlighting the need to share metadata for data discovery and access.

In a rapidly evolving data-sharing landscape, FEAGA collaborates with European and other international initiatives, like the 1+ Million Genomes (1+MG)⁶⁰ or the European Genomic Data Infrastructure (GDI)⁶¹, to serve a variety of human genomic data-sharing use-cases with its operational network for transnational discovery of and access to human data. The FEAGA architecture facilitates the core stages of the data management lifecycle, including data and metadata submission to CEAGA or FEAGA nodes, long-term and secure storage, **metadata publication for discovery**, data access request management, and controlled-access to data. These operations use encrypted data in secure environments, with user access managed through advanced authentication and authorisation systems. Interoperability is ensured by adhering to community standards, such as those developed by the Global Alliance for Genomics and Health (GA4GH)⁶². FEAGA nodes have the flexibility to implement or deploy components of their choice, provided they comply with these agreed-upon standards.

In the dynamic field of human genomics, creating **interoperable federated networks for discovery and access** is essential for maximizing data reuse. Building on updated resources and the expertise of the initial FEAGA nodes, more countries are establishing new nodes to enhance data sharing and collaboration. As the volume and diversity of data continue to grow, the supporting infrastructure must adapt to address these evolving challenges.

This document showcases **FEAGA's efforts on the topic of metadata standards** by focusing on a robust metadata framework to support its FAIR data-sharing goals. The current **CEAGA metadata model**⁶³, hereinafter the EGA v1 model, has been instrumental in enabling the registration and management of sensitive genomic data. However, as the scope of research expands and new technologies emerge, this reveals the need for the metadata

⁶⁰ <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/1-million-genomes>

⁶¹ <https://gdi.onemilliongenomes.eu/about/>

⁶² <https://www.ga4gh.org/about-us/>

⁶³ <https://ega-archive.org/submission/metadata/ega-schema>

model to accommodate complex data relationships and scenarios. Below, we outline how the **FEGA Metadata Working Group** (MWG) is building a sustainable model to manage and link metadata effectively, ensuring scalability, interoperability, and alignment with the wider research community.

3. Scope

This document outlines the FEGA MWG's **proposed abstract metadata model for FEGA, and its approach to metadata validation and linked data**. The model is designed to support robust, FAIR-compliant metadata within FEGA. While the model primarily serves the FEGA network (e.g., node maintainers and data curators), it is also intended as a resource for the **broader research community**, showcasing the working group's approach to improving FEGA's current metadata infrastructure.

The scope of this model includes defining **core metadata entities** (e.g., Biomaterial) and **relationships** (e.g., *Biomaterial UsedBy Process*) in FEGA's use-cases. Each element was developed based on well-established practices (e.g., JSON Schemas and RDF) and models from sources including the EGA v1 model. One of the main goals was to create a **long-term sustainable metadata model** to allow for potential adaptations and extensions, with clear emphasis on the experimental and analytical metadata. This abstract model serves both as: (1) a prospective foundation, as a community-led project, for an eventual EGA v2 metadata model implementation; and (2) as a publicly accessible metadata framework, available to external projects or institutions seeking to implement a similar approach. The fact that every piece of documentation and software is **open-source** demonstrates our commitment to engaging with the community.

This document does **not** address details of how the new metadata model may integrate with other external metadata models (e.g., BioSchemas) or projects (e.g., GDI), but lays the groundwork for future collaborative alignment.

The focus remains on creating a **scalable, open-source metadata model that aligns with FEGA's FAIR goals and can be adapted** to evolving research data needs over time.

4. Metadata model naming conventions

Before the FEGA MWG proposed the new EGA metadata model, **there was a single major version of the EGA model** from its start in 2008. Given the fact that the core source for the new model is the previous one, and in the interest of clear and traceable provenance in technical documentation, the naming conventions follow semantic versioning 2.0.0⁶⁴ and are as follows:

- **EGA v1 model**: the first major version of the EGA metadata model. It is, as of January 2026, the current metadata model, and has been in production (i.e., in use) since the establishment of the EGA in 2008. It is used, until the EGA v2 model is in production, by CEQA for submissions, and by FEGA nodes when sharing metadata with CEQA.

⁶⁴ <https://semver.org/#semantic-versioning-200>

- **EGA v2 model:** the second major iteration of the EGA metadata model, proposed by the FEGA MWG in this document, and the first major version to incorporate FEGA requirements. As of January 2026 it remains to be implemented.

The FEGA MWG aims for the EGA v2 model to be the common language for submission metadata across FEGA nodes, irrespective of the specific implementation of the model at each node, thus making this EGA v2 model the common metadata model for FEGA.

Find more details about the [Model versioning](#) and [Governance](#) in their respective sections.

5. User stories

[Table 1](#) outlines **user stories**, drafted as hypotheses to validate, that capture the needs and expectations of various stakeholders interacting with the EGA v2 metadata model. Each row identifies a **role** (*as a ...*), the specific **action** (*I want to ...*) they aim to perform, and the desired **result** (*to ...*) they seek to achieve. This structured format enables a clear understanding of how the model can address user needs, facilitate usability, and support interoperability across diverse contexts.

Table 1. User stories.

Role (<i>as a ...</i>)	Action (<i>I want to ...</i>)	Result (<i>to ...</i>)
Bioinformatician	Perform complex cross-FEGA archive queries	Support cross-archive dataset comparative analysis
Data consumer	Easily find data use policies of FEGA records	Make informed decisions about data use
Data consumer	Easily explore the metadata entities (e.g., knowledge graph)	Discover new suitable records for my research
Data curator	Validate metadata easily	Ensure metadata meets archive standards
Data curator	Validate metadata locally	Assess metadata compliance without sharing the metadata content
Data curator	Validate metadata locally	Assess metadata compliance without relying on third party services

Role (as a ...)	Action (I want to ...)	Result (to ...)
Data steward	Be able to use clear and standardised metadata structures	Support interoperable (e.g., with other archives) and diverse (e.g., in experimental types) submissions
Database administrator	Use a stable and versioned approach to FEQA identifiers	Maintain metadata traceability over time
Database administrator	Use a clear, open-source and versioned metadata validation system	Maintain traceability and transparency of used validation standards
External stakeholder	Reuse FEQA's metadata validation/linked data approach	Avoid duplicating effort developing metadata management frameworks, and be interoperable with FEQA
EGA v2 model maintainer	Easily manage change requests to the EGA v2 model	Ensure that the EGA v2 model is up to date with the user and field requirements
FEQA node maintainer	Have a consistent format for sharing FEQA metadata	Ensure seamless communication of metadata across FEQA nodes
FEQA node maintainer	Avoid data loss during model transitions	Adapt existing metadata in my node to the new model
FEQA node submitter	Enhance reusability, by using existing standards, ontologies and linked data	Increase the submitted metadata quality and interoperability
FEQA node submitter	Receive clear feedback on metadata-related errors	Promptly prepare submitted metadata in a compliant format
FEQA node submitter	Improve discoverability and reusability of my submitted metadata	Increase the citability of my submitted (meta)data both in research and grants

Role (as a ...)	Action (I want to ...)	Result (to ...)
FEGA operations committee member	Monitor adoption of the new metadata model	Ensure consistency across all nodes
GDI collaborator	Align metadata models between FEGA and GDI	Reduce duplication of effort across initiatives in overlapping nodes
Pipeline developer	Include metadata validation in automated workflows	Assert compliance of submitted metadata automatically
Data controller	Ensure metadata adheres to FAIR principles and relevant Ethical, Legal, and Social Implications (ELSI) requirements	Meet international frameworks and standards, and to approve submission to FEGA
Project coordinator	Demonstrate how metadata links across archives	Illustrate the benefits of interoperability, and motivate data silos to cooperate
Researcher	Access datasets linked to related publications	Facilitate my research

6. Methods

The methods described here outline the collaborative processes, tools, and strategies employed to achieve the objectives described above.

6.1. Collaboration across FEGA nodes

Structured group meetings were held monthly (1-hour sessions) starting September 2023. Communication channels included:

- **Slack:** A dedicated channel (*feqa_metadata_working_group*⁶⁵) in the ELIXIR workspace for day-to-day discussions.
- **Google Drive:** A Google Drive directory for collaborative documentation, questionnaires and storage of meeting notes.

⁶⁵ <https://elixir-europe.slack.com/archives/C05UHABF0CT>

- **Email:** Used for coordination and progress reports.
- **GitHub:** A repository (EGA-archive/feqa-metadata-schema⁶⁶) to manage schemas and technical reports. Additionally, contributors use forks⁶⁷ of the main repository to add changes.

6.2. Metadata modelling and validation

The EGA v2 model development focuses on aligning with FAIR principles, reusing existing standards, and integrating linked data concepts.

Key aspects of the modelling process include:

1. **Ontology Integration.** The MWG identified mappings to several widely adopted ontologies:
 - 1.1. **Basic descriptions of the model.** Including standards and vocabularies like: **schema.org**^{68,69} (e.g., `schema:description`⁷⁰), Simple Knowledge Organization System^{71,72} (**SKOS**, e.g., `skos:exactMatch`⁷³), Semantic Mapping Vocabulary⁷⁴ (**SEMAPV**, e.g., `semapv:LexicalMatching`⁷⁵) and Resource Description Framework Schema^{76,77} (**RDFS**, e.g., `rdfs:label`⁷⁸).
 - 1.2. **Provenance description.** For example, the Provenance Ontology^{79,80} (**PROV-O**, e.g., `prov:used`⁸¹) or Open Researcher and Contributor ID Schema⁸² (**ORCID iD Identifier Schema**, e.g., 0000-0002-7747-6256⁸³).
 - 1.3. **Field validation.** Enabling the model to include semantic validation based on ontologies like the Experimental Factor Ontology^{84,85} (**EFO**, e.g., `EFO:0002699`⁸⁶) or UBER anatomy ONtology (UBERON, e.g., `UBERON:0000992`⁸⁷).

⁶⁶ <https://github.com/EGA-archive/feqa-metadata-schema>

⁶⁷ <https://github.com/EGA-archive/feqa-metadata-schema/forks>

⁶⁸ schema.org

⁶⁹ <https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.hzdqz8>

⁷⁰ <https://schema.org/description>

⁷¹ <https://www.w3.org/TR/skos-reference>

⁷² <https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.48e326>

⁷³ <https://www.w3.org/TR/skos-reference/#exactMatch>

⁷⁴ <http://w3id.org/semapv/vocab/semapv.owl>

⁷⁵ <https://w3id.org/semapv/vocab/LexicalMatching>

⁷⁶ <https://www.w3.org/TR/rdf-schema>

⁷⁷ <https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.v9n3gk>

⁷⁸ https://www.w3.org/TR/rdf-schema/#ch_label

⁷⁹ <https://www.w3.org/TR/prov-o/>

⁸⁰ <https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.2rm2b3>

⁸¹ <https://www.w3.org/TR/prov-o/#used>

⁸² <https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.OrNi1L>

⁸³ <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-7747-6256>

⁸⁴ <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/efo/>

⁸⁵ <https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.1gr4tz>

⁸⁶ http://www.ebi.ac.uk/efo/EFO_0002699

⁸⁷ http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/UBERON_0000992

Ontologies were selected based on their relevance to FEGA use-cases and their adoption in widely used community standards and ecosystems. Additional ontologies will be incorporated as the model evolves.

2. **Field standards.** In line with the FEGA MWG's goal of creating a sustainable model, multiple existing standards are rendered into the EGA v2 model:

2.1. **Phenopackets**⁸⁸. Standardised, machine-readable schema for exchanging case-level phenotypic and disease information (e.g., disease⁸⁹), supporting consistent representation of individuals and biosamples across clinical and research settings.

2.2. **Beacon-v2**⁹⁰. GA4GH API specification enabling federated discovery of genomic and associated phenotypic datasets across distributed nodes using a common query/response framework

2.3. **BioSchemas**⁹¹. Community profiles built on schema.org to mark up life-science resources (e.g., computational workflow⁹²) for improved web discoverability and interoperability across registries and catalogues.

2.4. **Investigation Study Assay (ISA)**. ISA-JSON⁹³ metadata framework (e.g., process parameters⁹⁴) to structure experimental metadata across multi-omics workflows.

2.5. **Data Cataloguing**. Alignment with RDF-native catalogue standards: Data Catalog Vocabulary⁹⁵ (DCAT, e.g., dcat:Catalog⁹⁶) for catalogue interoperability, plus European application profiles (DCAT-AP⁹⁷ and HealthDCAT-AP⁹⁸) to represent dataset-level metadata consistently for cross-portal discovery (including European Health Data Space (EHDS)-oriented extensions).

3. **Validation Tools.**

3.1. **ELIXIR Biovalidator**⁹⁹. The primary tool for validating JSON documents against schemas, supporting API-based constraints, like ontology term checks through the Ontology Lookup Service¹⁰⁰ (OLS).

3.2. **JSON-LD Playground**¹⁰¹. Used for testing JSON-LD expansions and linked data principles.

⁸⁸ <https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.8f3fdc>

⁸⁹ <https://phenopacket-schema.readthedocs.io/en/latest/disease.html#disease>

⁹⁰ <https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.6fba91>

⁹¹ <https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.c3eae6>

⁹² <https://discovery.biothings.io/api/schema/bioschemasdrafts:ComputationalWorkflow/validation>

⁹³ <https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.yhLgTV>

⁹⁴ <https://isa-specs.readthedocs.io/en/latest/isajson.html#process-parameter-value-schema-json>

⁹⁵ <https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.h4j3qm>

⁹⁶ <https://www.w3.org/TR/vocab-dcat-3/#Class:Catalog>

⁹⁷ <https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.07f04a>

⁹⁸ <https://healthdataeu.pages.code.europa.eu/healthdcat-ap/releases/release-5/>

⁹⁹ <https://github.com/elixir-europe/biovalidator>

¹⁰⁰ <https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.Mkl9RR>

¹⁰¹ <https://json-ld.org/playground/>

- 3.3. **JSON Schema Validator**¹⁰². For general schema validation during schema development.
4. **JSON Schemas**. Albeit in progress, the EGA v2 model represents each entity (e.g., biomaterial) as a JSON file (e.g., `FEGA.biomaterial.json`¹⁰³) following the JSON Schema Specification¹⁰⁴ plus additional custom keywords defined by Biovalidator. These schemas include mappings, detailed property definitions, types, and constraints, ensuring robust validation and extensibility. JSON-LD Contexts (`@context`) are embedded directly within schemas to enable seamless JSON-to-JSON-LD transformations.
5. **Automation**. To aid with the continuous development of the EGA v2 model, scripts^{105,106} and workflows¹⁰⁷ are set in place to automate recurrent tasks (e.g., validation, release preparation, document linting) through GitHub workflows.

6.3. Namespace strategy

To maintain interoperability and establish a consistent identifier system, an `ega` entry¹⁰⁸ was created at `identifiers.org`¹⁰⁹, covering the resolution of EGA Stable IDs (e.g., `EGAD00001008392`¹¹⁰). This way, Compact Uniform Resource Identifiers (CURIEs) like `ega:EGAD00001008392` are uniquely resolved to the appropriate record through `identifiers.org`.

In the future, a `fega` namespace will be created to cover the heterogeneity of Persistent IDs (PIDs) within FEGA. This namespace would enable extensions via JSON-LD contexts at the federated level, supporting the creation of linked data graphs.

These namespaces align with FEGA's mission to support both internal metadata needs and broader interoperability.

6.4. Metadata validation

Validation, in its simplest form, entails comparing some "content" against some "rules", producing an evaluation of whether the content conforms to the rules. In the EGA v2 metadata model, validation couples a **domain-specific ruleset** (maintained as JSON Schema files) **with the ELIXIR Biovalidator**, providing syntactic validation and selected semantic checks (e.g., ontology term validation).

Our whole stack is **open-source**, **portable** and **scalable** (i.e., as many servers, wherever needed), making sure that the same validation outcome is reached regardless of the deployer (e.g., FEGA node, submitter).

¹⁰² <https://www.jsonschemavalidator.net/>

¹⁰³ <https://github.com/M-casado/fega-metadata-schema/blob/main/schemas/FEGA.biomaterial.json>

¹⁰⁴ <https://json-schema.org/specification>

¹⁰⁵ <https://github.com/M-casado/fega-metadata-schema/tree/main/scripts/py>

¹⁰⁶ https://github.com/M-casado/fega-metadata-schema/tree/main/src/fega_tools

¹⁰⁷ <https://github.com/M-casado/fega-metadata-schema/tree/main/.github/workflows>

¹⁰⁸ <https://registry.identifiers.org/registry/ega>

¹⁰⁹ <https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.n14rc8>

¹¹⁰ <https://identifiers.org/ega:EGAD00001008392>

The set of JSON Schemas contains the "rules" and can be referenced within a metadata JSON document via its `schema` attribute. The "content" (i.e., metadata) is formatted as JSON as well and is contained within the `data` attribute of a JSON document. A JSON instance is declared *valid* when every assertion in the corresponding JSON Schema succeeds. For example, the data¹¹¹ in `biomaterial-valid_1.json` is valid when it passes all constraints specified in the same document's schema¹¹².

JSON Schema specification (draft 2020-12¹¹³) and custom keywords from ELIXIR Biovalidator¹¹⁴ provide the groundwork for the FEGA Schemas to encode domain-specific constraints (e.g., required fields, ontology checks). For further details, refer to the schemas' documentation¹¹⁵ in the GitHub repository.

The FEGA metadata schemas are built for **continuous development**. See more details at the [Model versioning](#) section.

6.4.1. Running validation

Validating data through the EGA v2 model is plain and simple: it requires access to a **Biovalidator endpoint and feeding it a JSON document**. To interact with the validator, Biovalidator can be deployed locally or you can use a provided API (e.g., `biovalidator.ega.ebi.ac.uk/validate`¹¹⁶). When Biovalidator is deployed locally or elsewhere, a `/validate` endpoint is exposed and accepts JSON documents containing both the schema and data, or references to them. This same endpoint outputs the result of the validation when used. Further details about deploying Biovalidator can be found at its GitHub repository¹¹⁷.

The group has created onboarding materials on this matter, including a dedicated FEGA Metadata Technical Deep Dive¹¹⁸ and succinct posters^{119,120,121}. Furthermore, an example of the end-to-end validation workflow can be found in the automated `json_validation_deploying_biovalidator.yml`¹²². In fact, it can be manually triggered for maintainers who are not proficient at coding, easing the assertion of data validation even further.

¹¹¹

https://github.com/M-casado/fega-metadata-schema/blob/774392bbb4ad446f7d39226a6ce17111ac258557/data/jsonld/biomaterial-valid_1.json#L5-L66

¹¹²

https://github.com/M-casado/fega-metadata-schema/blob/774392bbb4ad446f7d39226a6ce17111ac258557/data/jsonld/biomaterial-valid_1.json#L2-L4

¹¹³ <https://json-schema.org/draft/2020-12/schema>

¹¹⁴

<https://github.com/elixir-europe/biovalidator?tab=readme-ov-file#extended-keywords-for-ontology-and-taxonomy-validation>

¹¹⁵ <https://github.com/M-casado/fega-metadata-schema/tree/main/schemas#overview>

¹¹⁶ <http://biovalidator.ega.ebi.ac.uk/validate> - Note that this endpoint is not actively maintained.

¹¹⁷ <https://github.com/elixir-europe/biovalidator>

¹¹⁸ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14968151>

¹¹⁹ <https://doi.org/10.7490/f1000research.1120212.1>

¹²⁰ <https://doi.org/10.7490/f1000research.1119732.1>

¹²¹ <https://doi.org/10.7490/f1000research.1119417.1>

¹²²

https://github.com/M-casado/fega-metadata-schema/blob/main/.github/workflows/json_validation_deploying_biovalidator.yml

6.5. RDF and linked data

In order to provide `@context` to the FEGA schemas and data to make them RDF-friendly, we extensively used the JSON-LD Playground¹²³ and JSON-LD 1.1 documentation¹²⁴.

6.5.1. Framing

When combining JSON Schemas and Linked data, we faced the issue of balancing between the **flexibility of JSON-LD and the stringency of JSON Schemas**. On one hand, RDF modelled metadata is extremely flexible in format (e.g., Turtle, JSON-LD) and structure (e.g., expanded, compacted, flattened). On the other hand, JSON Schema has strict requirements to maintain our standards during validation. These JSON Schemas expect metadata to be in a specific format and follow a specific structure.

Several solutions for this challenge were taken into consideration. For example, flattening and compacting all JSON-LDs before validation, or being stringent with the expected format of JSON-LD documents we validated.

Lastly, the chosen path is to use **framing**¹²⁵, which allows us to map a specific structure for all incoming and flattened JSON-LD files. Through framing, we are able to **change JSON-LD files to a format that the EGA v2 model JSON Schemas** were created to validate. The EGA v2 frames, still in development (see `frames/`¹²⁶), will define the structure FEGA expects for each of the main entities. When these frames are applied to a flattened JSON-LD document containing such entities, we can reformat them into a structured JSON-LD with that entity type as root, and thus make them suitable for validation through the EGA v2 model JSON Schemas. In summary, framing allows us to transform RDF-data into a format compatible with the EGA v2 model JSON Schemas.

7. EGA v2 metadata model

The EGA v2 model has two main components to highlight, both tightly intertwined: the **conceptual model** and the **technology stack**. The former consists of the way information is structured and linked (e.g., how a blood sample is represented), while the latter represents the chosen implementation approaches (e.g., how to assert submissions comply with the conceptual model). They are difficult to split apart, as both complement each other, and thus throughout this document we refer to both together as "EGA v2 model" or "EGA v2 metadata model".

¹²³ <https://json-ld.org/playground/>

¹²⁴ Sporny, M., Kellogg, G., Lanthaler, M., & Lindström, N. (2020, July 16). *JSON-LD 1.1: A JSON-based Serialization for Linked Data*. W3C Recommendation. Retrieved from <https://www.w3.org/TR/json-ld11/>

¹²⁵ <https://w3c.github.io/json-ld-syntax/#framed-document-form>

¹²⁶ <https://github.com/M-casado/fega-metadata-schema/tree/main/frames>

7.1. Group formation and work summary

The FEGA MWG engaged CEGA and **multiple nodes**: Germany, Poland, Norway, Finland, Portugal, Sweden, Spain, Canada and, later, Switzerland. The group (i.e., we) worked collaboratively as per the timeline shown in [Figure 3](#), and detailed below.

Initial efforts in October 2023 involved **presenting existing metadata models and requirements** from five nodes and GDI. In January 2024, a survey was circulated to explore the metadata landscape, receiving 10 responses from 8 countries, including CEGA, FEGA Germany, FEGA Poland, FEGA Norway, FEGA Finland, FEGA Portugal, FEGA Sweden and FEGA Spain.

After collecting the feedback from the survey, we worked through **rounds of drafting** followed by feedback, culminating in a **first draft of the abstract model by July 2024**, presented to external stakeholders. See [External Involvement](#) for further details.

In the second half of 2024, we continued with further rounds of external reviews and outreach, engaging diverse participants in workshops and presentations. Taken together, all the feedback helped shape the EGA v2 model. At the beginning of 2025, we started putting all our efforts into this **technical report and the feга-metadata-schema repository**¹²⁷.

Figure 3. Overview of the timeline from the MWG.

7.2. External involvement

External collaboration included interactions with ELIXIR, GDI, GA4GH, Beacon, BioSchemas and other stakeholders:

1. **GDI** requirements were presented in early MWG meetings, aiming for eventual alignment or convergence of metadata models. Furthermore, participants of the FEGA MWG are also involved in GDI's metadata squad¹²⁸ and the GDI-Beacon metadata workshops¹²⁹.
2. Outreach through **conferences, workshops, and external stakeholder meetings** ensured feedback from diverse stakeholders, including the European Nucleotide

¹²⁷ <https://github.com/M-casado/feга-metadata-schema>

¹²⁸ <https://gdi-elixir.slack.com/archives/C07D6GFJ3LH>

¹²⁹ https://docs.google.com/document/d/18ZPfdwucj8eaiUDbnyS5F9DaUzR1BGvhTf42H_maZKw

Archive^{130,131} (ENA), National Bioinformatics Infrastructure Sweden¹³² (NBIS), and the Japanese Genotype-phenotype Archive^{133,134} (JGA), among many others.

To gather feedback and ensure broad adoption of the metadata model, the MWG engaged in several outreach activities:

- Distributing multiple **forms** across national and international consortia:
 - "Presentations" form¹³⁵ to organise the kick-off of the group.
 - "Model mapping" form¹³⁶ to collect inputs for the initial design of the EGA v2 metadata model.
 - "Federated EGA metadata model poster feedback" form¹³⁷ to gather feedback from participants of the 2024 ELIXIR All Hands meeting¹³⁸ in Uppsala, Sweden.
 - "Metadata feedback" form¹³⁹ during the 2024 ELIXIR Federated Human Data¹⁴⁰ (FHD) Community Day¹⁴¹ in Lisbon, Portugal.
 - "Accessibility of FEGA metadata" form¹⁴² to gather insight on the exposure of metadata through FEGA. The results were presented¹⁴³ to the FEGA group and discussed, prompting the organisation of a Metadata Accessibility Workshop in 2026.
- **Presentations at major workshops:**
 - GDI Pillar II Metadata Workshop¹⁴⁴ (March 2024).
 - ELIXIR Federated Human Data Community Day¹⁴⁵ (Nov 2024).
 - BioSchemas Community Day¹⁴⁶ (Jan 2025).
 - FEGA Technical Deep dive¹⁴⁷ (March 2025).
 - GA4GH Beacon for Metadata Discovery¹⁴⁸ (March 2025)

¹³⁰ <http://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena>

¹³¹ <https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.dj8nt8>

¹³² <https://nbis.se/>

¹³³ <https://www.ddbj.nig.ac.jp/jga>

¹³⁴ <https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.pwgf4p>

¹³⁵ <https://forms.gle/bDacFij9Mz7xWUHA9>

¹³⁶ <https://forms.gle/Sw1k7SRiEG8YUpoL7>

¹³⁷ <https://forms.gle/h5ZWsvL73djgaduW6>

¹³⁸ <https://elixir-events.eventscase.com/EN/ahm2024>

¹³⁹ <https://forms.gle/8JN4bGJrY5EfmY15A>

¹⁴⁰ <https://elixir-europe.org/communities/human-data>

¹⁴¹ <https://elixir-europe.org/events/elixir-federated-human-data-community-day-0>

¹⁴² <https://forms.gle/iT1revnW5foeDREy8>

¹⁴³ <https://docs.google.com/presentation/d/1Vue9BFoURdBg8ZWta20r4kx17YunAH4ny8j7gGWOoNw>

¹⁴⁴ https://docs.google.com/presentation/d/16M7c1-p1NxjraQQWNa_Tgg4ya-g4qNOkUu3sMsJmeuA

¹⁴⁵ <https://docs.google.com/presentation/d/1lwPS2OBcoJJuaPnz0OIC7JoT4sMcOyXS>

¹⁴⁶ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14726856>

¹⁴⁷ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14968151>

¹⁴⁸ https://docs.google.com/document/d/1LHvH2nMs0MMjEYdIEtzCAUB442D_83SZ

- Predictor Effector Gene (PEG) working group¹⁴⁹ (July 2025).
- ELIXIR Federated Human Data Community Day¹⁵⁰ (Nov 2025).
- A dedicated **external stakeholders meeting** in July 2024, presenting the "Pruned FEGA Abstract Metadata Model"¹⁵¹, and gathering feedback from 25 participants covering diverse projects and teams, such as German National Cohort¹⁵² (NAKO), GA4GH, ENA, NBIS, Beacon, GDI and JGA.
- Creation of the following **posters**:
 - "Improving metadata compliance and interoperability at EGA with Biovalidator"¹⁵³, presented at the ELIXIR All Hands Meeting in June 2023¹⁵⁴, in Dublin, Ireland.
 - "Advancing Genomic Data Interoperability: The FEGA Metadata Model"¹⁵⁵, presented at the ELIXIR All Hands Meeting in June 2024, in Uppsala, Sweden.
 - "Unifying FEGA metadata: A standardized model for multimodal data"¹⁵⁶, presented at the ELIXIR All Hands Meeting in June 2025¹⁵⁷, in Thessaloniki, Greece.
- Collaboration from **experts in omics** fields through the use-case sessions (see [Use-cases](#)).
- Creation of this **technical report** to disseminate progress and outcomes.

These activities (and subsequent word-of-mouth) encouraged researchers from a wider network (e.g., PEG, The International Genome Sample Resource¹⁵⁸) to connect with the FEGA MWG about metadata models.

7.3. Model entities

During the development of the EGA v2 metadata model, we adopted a **process-centered approach** that emphasises procedural representations over traditional biological experiment or analysis perspectives. See examples of these differences in [Figure 8](#) and [Figure 9](#). This shift allows for a more flexible and comprehensive framework, capable of representing a wide array of processes, not limited to canonical experimental designs. Our approach draws

¹⁴⁹ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16087281>

¹⁵⁰ https://docs.google.com/presentation/d/1piixarPwVnYqGes-RZbL9xocwb1_g8pggdrzoP3-3E

¹⁵¹ https://docs.google.com/presentation/d/1EtoLU_08XaH8NOTm9_ITTZkwfMwPhPQXjk1jGxEiivA

¹⁵² <https://nako.de/en/study>

¹⁵³ <https://doi.org/10.7490/f1000research.1119417.1>

¹⁵⁴ <https://elixir-europe.org/events/elixir-all-hands-2023>

¹⁵⁵ <https://doi.org/10.7490/f1000research.1119732.1>

¹⁵⁶ <https://doi.org/10.7490/f1000research.1120212.1>

¹⁵⁷ <https://elixir-events.eventscase.com/EN/ahm2025>

¹⁵⁸ <https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.4Vs9VM>

inspiration from models such as the Human Cell Atlas^{159,160} (HCA) and the SEEK workflow model^{161,162}, which have successfully implemented similar methodologies.

The entities defined in the EGA v2 model are as follows. Each of them listed here with its name (e.g., Biomaterial), the closest match to an ontology term (e.g., [OBI:0100051](#) – not necessarily the only mapping, a replacement, or a 1-to-1 match), and its definition in the EGA v2 model.

- **Biomaterial** ([OBI:0100051](#)¹⁶³): Represents any biological material, from whole organisms (including humans) to subcellular components and macromolecules (e.g., DNA samples).
- **Protocol** ([prov:Plan](#)¹⁶⁴): Detailed plan of instructions on how a procedure is done. For example, sample preparation, sequencing or feature extraction techniques. See [Disambiguation](#).
- **Process** ([prov:Activity](#)¹⁶⁵): A specific execution of a protocol or procedure, applied to specific inputs (Biomaterial or Datafile) and producing specific outputs (Biomaterial or Datafile). See [Disambiguation](#).
- **Datafile** ([dcat:Distribution](#)¹⁶⁶): A resource containing data. Includes a diverse range of formats (e.g., BAM, VCF, mzML) from multiple life science domains (e.g., genomics, imaging, phenoclinical, proteomics). See [Disambiguation](#).
- **Dataset** ([dcat:Dataset](#)¹⁶⁷): A collection of Datafiles¹⁶⁸, published or curated by a single agent, and available for access or download in one or more representations. Datasets are subject to a particular policy for controlled-access, commonly making them the units of access distribution. See [Disambiguation](#).
- **Policy** ([dcterms:RightsStatement](#)¹⁶⁹): Data access policy, governing how data is processed, protected, and shared. It can include, for example, data use conditions and references to the dataset's Data Access Agreement (DAA).
- **Data Access Committee (DAC)** ([prov:Agent](#)¹⁷⁰): Body managing data access requests, overseeing the approval process for data usage in accordance with its defined Policy.

¹⁵⁹ <https://data.humancellatlas.org/metadata>

¹⁶⁰ Regev, A., Teichmann, S. A., Lander, E. S., Amit, I., Benoist, C., Birney, E., ... & Human Cell Atlas Meeting Participants. (2017). The human cell atlas. *elife*, 6, e27041.

¹⁶¹ <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-12-385118-5.00029-3>

¹⁶² Wolstencroft, K., Owen, S., Du Preez, F., Krebs, O., Mueller, W., Goble, C., & Snoep, J. L. (2011). The SEEK: a platform for sharing data and models in systems biology. In *Methods in enzymology* (Vol. 500, pp. 629-655). Academic Press.

¹⁶³ http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/OBI_0100051

¹⁶⁴ <https://www.w3.org/TR/prov-o/#Plan>

¹⁶⁵ <https://www.w3.org/TR/prov-o/#Activity>

¹⁶⁶ <https://www.w3.org/TR/vocab-dcat-3/#Class:Distribution>

¹⁶⁷ <https://www.w3.org/TR/vocab-dcat-3/#Class:Dataset>

¹⁶⁸ At first, the group defined the Dataset as a compilation of processes, instead of Datafiles. Therefore, there may be discrepancies notable in the graphs created during the initial use-case sessions.

¹⁶⁹ <http://purl.org/dc/terms/RightsStatement>

¹⁷⁰ <https://www.w3.org/TR/prov-o/#Agent>

- **Study** ([schema:ResearchProject](https://schema.org/ResearchProject)¹⁷¹): Compilation of Protocol Collections (e.g., examinations, analyses or critical inspections) applied to investigate a particular topic within the context of a given Project.
- **Cohort** ([prov:Collection](https://www.w3.org/TR/prov-o/#Collection)¹⁷²): A group of Biomaterials (e.g., individuals, biopsies) sharing specific characteristics, facilitating comparative studies and discovery.
- **Project** ([schema:Project](https://schema.org/Project)¹⁷³): Umbrella record that groups related Studies and Datasets under a single scientific or funding scope.
- **Protocol collection** ([prov:Collection](https://www.w3.org/TR/prov-o/#Collection), [prov:Plan](https://www.w3.org/TR/prov-o/#Plan)): A versioned set of Protocol records that together define a complete workflow. May include a single or multiple protocols, depending on the desired granularity by the submitter. See [Disambiguation](#).
- **Catalog** ([dcat:Catalog](https://www.w3.org/TR/vocab-dcat-3/#Class:Catalog)¹⁷⁴): Curated collection of metadata about all Datasets exposed by CEGA or a FEGA node.
- **Catalog Record** ([dcat:CatalogRecord](https://www.w3.org/TR/vocab-dcat-3/#Class:Catalog_Record)¹⁷⁵): Administrative entity that logs the registration details (e.g., date, agent, status) for a single Dataset (its primary topic) within CEGA's/FEGA nodes' catalogs.

To see these entities in use, refer to the examples in the [Use-cases](#) section.

7.4. Model cardinality

A simplified version of the EGA v2 model can be seen in a diagram in [Figure 4](#). In it, we represent a quick, **five-block overview**: biomaterial, activities, datafiles, and the administrative and data management layers.

¹⁷¹ <https://schema.org/ResearchProject>

¹⁷² <https://www.w3.org/TR/prov-o/#Collection>

¹⁷³ <https://schema.org/Project>

¹⁷⁴ <https://www.w3.org/TR/vocab-dcat-3/#Class:Catalog>

¹⁷⁵ https://www.w3.org/TR/vocab-dcat-3/#Class:Catalog_Record

Figure 4. Flow diagram representing an oversimplification of the model entities and relationships of the EGA v2 metadata model.

The summarised view of [Figure 4](#) is expanded further in [Figure 5](#), with mapped terms (e.g., `dcat:Distribution`) and semantically tagged relationships (e.g., `prov:wasUsedBy`). Domain namespaces in the diagram are:

- **prov:** Provenance¹⁷⁶.
- **dcat:** Data Catalog Vocabulary¹⁷⁷.
- **dcterms:** Dublin Core Metadata Initiative Terms¹⁷⁸.
- **schema:** Schema.org¹⁷⁹.
- **foaf:** Friend of a Friend¹⁸⁰.

¹⁷⁶ <https://www.w3.org/ns/prov>

¹⁷⁷ <http://www.w3.org/ns/dcat>

¹⁷⁸ <http://purl.org/dc/terms>

¹⁷⁹ <http://schema.org>

¹⁸⁰ <http://xmlns.com/foaf/0.1>

Cardinality constraints (e.g., "*how many datafiles can a process generate*") need to be further defined (ongoing discussions).

Furthermore, note that cardinality between the model entities in [Figure 5](#) is classified as:

- **Core.** Implies the default connections between entities envisioned by the model. In other words, the source of truth for how to link parts of the model.
- **Implementation.** Corresponds to inferred relationships that may help with querying the model once it is in use. These are mere suggestions to facilitate the recovery of information through queries, based on common discoverability patterns (e.g., a user requesting to know which cohorts participated in a study), and should be based on, not replace, the core ones.

7.4.1. Disambiguations

Given the highly heterogeneous ways in which entities can be used by the researchers and submitters, their definitions are defined broadly. Nevertheless, to facilitate the submission and querying of metadata, in this section we further disambiguate the nuances between entities, narrowing their use.

7.4.1.1. Processes and Protocols

A Process (`prov:Activity`) is linked to the applied collection of protocols (i.e., plans) using `prov:hadPlan`¹⁸¹. In these protocols, agents (`prov:Agent`, e.g., a lab technician) adopted different roles in the context of the activity (e.g., DNA extraction) to transform an input (e.g., blood sample biomaterial) into an output (e.g., DNA sample biomaterial).

Linking the individual protocols and the activities is the Protocol Collection: the "plan at this granularity", where submitters have freedom over how many protocols are applied in each process. Groupings by Protocol Collection highly resemble the legacy groupings of Experiment or Analysis in the EGA v1 model.

This distinction supports different representations (see [Figure 6](#) and [Figure 13](#)) of the plans based on the given detail:

- **Coarse submission** (few processes, multiple protocols per process). One process points (via `prov:hadPlan`) to one Protocol Collection (which is the composite plan). This collection lists the individual protocols as members of its grouping via `prov:hadMember`¹⁸².
This setting would correspond to the canonical EGA v1 Experiment definition, for example, where multiple protocols (e.g., sample preparation, DNA extraction, sequencing) were grouped under a single collection (i.e., the experiment).
- **Detailed submission** (multiple processes, one or multiple protocols per process). The overall workflow is split into numerous processes, having a granular step-by-step chain of input-process-output.
This approach would suit a detailed design, where data of each activity (e.g., execution date, performers) were known, and thus structured as individual nodes of a process tree.

¹⁸¹ <https://www.w3.org/TR/prov-o/#hadPlan>

¹⁸² <https://www.w3.org/TR/prov-o/#hadMember>

Figure 6. Visual representation of the different process trees based on the submission granularity.

Examples of these two can be found in the [Microarray](#) use-case section.

It is important to note that `prov:hadMember` expresses membership alone, not ordering. The main aim of the model is not to contain the full and detailed protocol information of each activity, but the information to enable discoverability of data. Therefore, protocol order was not deemed worth bringing into the mix. If this were to change, other models such as P-Plan¹⁸³ could be considered.

On a different note, **processes** can be classified in **four categories** (see [Table 2](#), [Figure 7](#)) depending on the input-output combinations. These categories are merely informative, and are foreseen to greatly help users discover relevant datasets in EGA.

Table 2. Classification of processes based on input-output combinations.

		Output	
		Biomaterial	Datafile
Input	Biomaterial	Sample preparation	Assay
	Datafile	Synthetic biology	Analysis

It is important to understand the differences and similarities between EGA v1 and v2 with respect to processes. What in EGA v1 is represented by experiments and analyses, in EGA v2 is represented by sequential processes of different types. In [Figure 7](#), these similarities are visualized by encompassing the processes of a mock example in what would be their

¹⁸³ https://www.opmw.org/model/p-plan/#figure_mapping_example

corresponding representations in EGA v1 and v2 conceptual models. See further details at the [CEGA use-case](#) section.

Figure 7. Classification of processes and comparison of EGA v1 experiments/analysis and EGA v2 processes.

7.4.1.2. Datasets and Datafiles

In DCAT, datasets carry "dataset-level" descriptive metadata, while distributions carry "delivery/access" metadata (e.g., download URLs, media type, byte size).

DCAT notes that distributions of one dataset "should broadly contain the same data". This view of datasets and distributions in DCAT **partly conflicts** with the canonical EGA v1 model definition, where datafiles are parts of a dataset, and not alternative ways to access the same data. Nevertheless, DCAT also states that the boundary between "same dataset, multiple distributions" versus "different datasets" is application-specific and up to community practice. There is no expectation that different downloadable distributions must contain exactly equivalent information. For example, different distributions **might include or exclude different subsets** of the entire dataset.

In order to avoid highly nested datasets (i.e., each Datafile being a Dataset) and overly complicated Datafile metadata, EGA v2 adopts in this model the **practical convention** that: (1) a **Dataset** corresponds to the **collection of datafiles** under the same Policy; while (2) **Datafiles** are the **file-level distributions** that make up a Dataset.

7.5. Use-cases

In this section, we review **metadata modelling use-cases that the FEGA community may face** and show how each one maps to the proposed EGA v2 metadata model, side-by-side with the current EGA v1 model when relevant. The goal is to reassure the community that their data is represented seamlessly through, and thus encourage the adoption of, the EGA v2 model.

Each of these use-cases has been worked through as a **community effort**, by setting up "*FEGA Use-case sessions*", open to everyone, where a volunteer presented an example dataset and the attendees, including experts in the field, modelled it in detail using the EGA v2 model entities.

These sessions were held in the order shown below. The large Excalidraw¹⁸⁴ diagrams ([Annexes 1 to 4](#)) are snapshots from those sessions: they capture the hands-on work and discussions, but may not reflect the final model in every detail. Treat them as historical evidence of the process, not as authoritative diagrams. The mermaid diagrams and written explanations in each use-case are up to date, and note any model changes that occurred after each session.

To date, the MWG has organised **four use-case sessions**: (1) CEGA; (2) Microarray; (3) Proteomics; and (4) Microbiome. Based on the discussion held during the ELIXIR Federated Human Data (FHD) Community Day^{185,186} 2025 in Lausanne, Switzerland, future use-case session candidates are: Cohorts/Biobanks, Imaging, Phenotypic/Clinical (e.g., longitudinal study), Single-cell Sequencing, and Exposome. We welcome any suggestions for other possible scenarios that should be tested with the model and are different to the existing ones.

7.5.1. CEGA use-case

Here we describe the session held by the MWG, use a submission example and summarise its outcomes, working out an updated representation of a CEGA submission (natively in EGA v1 model) using the EGA v2 model. For further details (slides, recording, diagrams, etc.), please refer to the session agenda¹⁸⁷.

In this use-case, we went through the most common CEGA submission type: **genomics**. Given that attendees brought their own datasets to model, the group split into:

- An **example synthetic dataset** (EGAD00001008392¹⁸⁸) submitted to CEGA. This was the example that attendees of groups A and B (see [Annex 1](#)) took during the hands-on session.
- A **real-world submission in progress**, brought by Robin Liechti. This was the example that group C (see [Annex 1](#)) took during the hands-on session.

¹⁸⁴ <https://plus.excalidraw.com/>

¹⁸⁵ <https://elixir-europe.org/events/fhd-hdtr-day>

¹⁸⁶ https://docs.google.com/document/d/1TSROVqmBXC1ZOzpy_3Zqpu60GHuFrDObyCap83YjtW4

¹⁸⁷ https://docs.google.com/document/d/178nspglT_N4F52IVZpaNCnbXDSjnCFiGMpsSMO7ricc

¹⁸⁸ <https://ega-archive.org/datasets/EGAD00001008392>

7.5.1.1. Key session outcomes

- The **EGA v2 model can adequately represent the most common CEQA submission** type (sequencing) without losing information.
- The **Protocol Collection** entity was added to the EGA v2 model.

7.5.1.2. Worked example

Below, we model in detail the **synthetic dataset example** (EGAD00001008392). In doing so, we pinpoint the **similarities and overlapping semantic entities across models**, bridging both the EGA v1 and v2 metadata models.

For the sake of simplicity, we do **not** cover all entities in this dataset, given how verbose the output diagram would be. Nevertheless, we go over types that are different across models, with sufficient coverage for this exercise. For further details about the dataset itself, please request access¹⁸⁹ to the dataset, which is managed by CEQA. Alternatively, you can see a summary of the dataset in the slides¹⁹⁰ of the session.

To understand the transition from EGA v1 to EGA v2 models, we need to clarify one of the key differences: **modularity of processes**. As explained in the [Model entities](#) section, and depicted in [Figure 7](#) and [Figure 8](#), when we have a sample in the EGA v1 model, it can be linked to datafiles either through **EXPERIMENTS** and **RUNS**, or through **ANALYSES**. Meanwhile, the EGA v2 model simply represents them as different types of **procedural steps**, each with its specific protocol collection and process.

¹⁸⁹ <https://ega-archive.org/datasets/EGAD00001008392/request>

¹⁹⁰ https://docs.google.com/presentation/d/1maxcv1lupnJtkMbw2I7h82CJQOFgk_Lx-HkvF1fadQ

Figure 8. Representation of the same sequencing and alignment processes in both the EGA v1 and v2 models.

Now let us replace the placeholder names (e.g., Datafile) with the **real identifiers and given names** from the example dataset, and explore the differences across models (see [Figure 9](#)). In the synthetic dataset, sample `EGAN00003364608` (named `case2_father`), was used by a sequencing experiment (`EGAX00002583878`), associated with a run (`EGAR00003021169`) that contains two datafiles (two FASTQ files).

This can be represented in a simple way through the EGA v2 model: a **biomaterial** (`case2_father`) was used as **input in a process** that followed two protocols (library preparation and sequencing) and produced as **output two FASTQ files**.

If we go one step further, we start to see the **utility of the EGA v2 model and its modularity**. The way the original dataset was modelled in the EGA v1 model, these two FASTQ files were used in an analysis (`EGAZ00001743989`) to create an alignment (BAM) file. At first glance, it looks apparent in the EGA v1 model that these two FASTQ files were the input for such an analysis, but this is an **implicit association** based on the filenames. In other words, **in the EGA v1 model there is no direct linkage between the FASTQ and BAM files**.

On the other hand, in the **EGA v2 model**, we **explicitly** indicate that the quality control and alignment process had these two FASTQ files as inputs, creating a **procedural sequence**: a material entity (the biomaterial sample) was sequenced, and its sequencing files were aligned to produce a BAM file.

Figure 9. Representation in detail (with real accessions) of the same sequencing and alignment processes in both the EGA v1 and v2 models.

Similarly, we could continue down this route where, in this same dataset, each sample has 24 VCF files derived from a variant calling process, using their respective BAM files as inputs. All these analyses sit as individual entities in the EGA v1 model, while they form a process tree in the future approach, enabling provenance tracking.

Regarding **administrative** (Study) and **data management entities** (Dataset, Policy and DAC), the representation would be extremely similar across models (see [Figure 10](#) and [Figure 11](#)). The main differences are the cardinality between entities, rather than the entities themselves. For example, a dataset in the EGA v1 model is linked to analyses and runs, while in the EGA v2 model it is connected to datafiles.

Figure 10. Representation in detail (with real accessions) of the whole worked CEGA example modelled through EGA v1 model.

Figure 11. Representation in detail (with real accessions) of the worked CEGA example, modelled through the EGA v2 model.

7.5.2. Microarray

During a dedicated "Microarray" session (see [Annex 2](#)), the MWG went through a **simple two-colour experiment** in which two cancer patients (individual A and B) each provided a tumour and a matched normal tissue sample. RNA is isolated, reverse-transcribed, labelled with dyes and co-hybridised on the same microarray slide. TIFF images are generated by scanning the tissues, and downstream software generates intensity files (*.idat) and an expression matrix. Phenotypic and disease metadata for each patient are captured using GA4GH Phenopackets. For further details (slides, recording, diagrams...), please refer to the session **agenda**¹⁹¹.

7.5.2.1. Key session outcomes

1. The **EGA v2 model can adequately represent microarray** experiments.
2. The amount of **intermediary entities** (biomaterials from individuals A and B in [Annex 2](#)) depends on the granularity that the submitter can (or is willing to) provide.
3. **"Project"** entity was added to the EGA v2 model.

7.5.2.2. Worked example

As introduced above, this use-case revolved around **two fictitious individuals: A and B**, who, in summary, had **clinical information, samples assayed, and analysis** performed on their data.

During the session, we made use of these two individuals to **represent the possible differences in granularity** across submissions. In this example, submission for individual B had more intermediary steps (e.g., mRNA and cDNA biomaterials) than the one for individual A.

The simplest scenario was represented through **individual A** (i.e., a biomaterial of type organism 'A'). In this case, following [Figure 12](#), through sample preparation, two tissue samples were obtained: control and case (tumour). These samples were then processed following an encompassing protocol collection, which included steps from RNA isolation to scanning. The output of this process was a set of files, including raw intensity files.

Finally, the intensity files, combined with other input files, were used following another analytical protocol collection and produced the differential expression matrices.

¹⁹¹ https://docs.google.com/document/d/1VCJ3qF4ShggiNrnLxtLFIH_h8J5-J2aeiUKt37aUMd8

Figure 12. Representation (in EGA v2 model) of a simplified view for individual A, except for clinical information.

The metadata of the submission for **individual B** is very similar to the one above (see [Figure 13](#)). The only difference is that we are creating an intermediary entity, a biomaterial of type cDNA, in between the tissue biomaterial and the datafiles. This would be the case if the submitter had information specifically about that new intermediary biomaterial that could be informative (e.g., when it was obtained, where, under which conditions...). These two correspond to the coarse and detailed submission types introduced in the [Processes and Protocols](#) section.

To account for this new granularity, the model simply splits the protocol collection that was encompassing all these steps into two different protocol collections:

1. **RNA isolation and reverse transcription.** The one that is followed to transform the tissue biomaterial into the cDNA biomaterial.
2. **Labelling, hybridisation and scanning.** The one that enables obtaining the datafiles from the cDNA biomaterial.

Figure 13. Comparison of differences between examples for individual B and A in EGA v2 model.

For the sake of simplicity in visualization, the **clinical information** was separated into a different diagram (see [Figure 14](#)). As observed in the figure, the two individuals were the input of a clinical record extraction protocol, where the output is their combined phenoclinical information in the format of a phenopacket.

Figure 14. Representation of clinical information for both individuals A and B in EGA v2 model.

7.5.3. Proteomics

The proteomics use case addresses important **metadata representation gaps** previously identified in the current EGA v1 model, which was primarily genomics-centric and lacked dedicated fields or concepts tailored for proteomics data submissions.

Proteomics datasets, often deposited in repositories such as the PRoteomics IDentifications Database^{192,193} (PRIDE) under the ProteomeXchange consortium^{194,195}, require capturing nuanced submission information, including experiment types and the specific file formats generated by mass spectrometry workflows. The FEQA MWG, through a thorough

¹⁹² <https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.e1byny>

¹⁹³ <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/pride/markdownpage/citationpage>

¹⁹⁴ <https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.92dt9d>

¹⁹⁵ <https://www.proteomexchange.org/>

pre-workshop analysis and hands-on workshop session, has refined the metadata model to accommodate those needs effectively. The details can be found in the use-case agenda¹⁹⁶.

Use-case workshop

In this section, we describe the Proteomics session ([Annex 3](#)) held by the FEGA MWG and summarise its outcomes—specifically, how a **proteomics dataset containing human mass spectrometry data can be represented by the EGA v2 metadata model**. Mapping such a submission involves aligning core information (e.g., sample details, data acquisition methods) and file formats with FEGA requirements.

[PXD006482](#)¹⁹⁷ is the **original dataset submitted to the PRIDE** database. This dataset ("*Identification of Missing Proteins in the Phosphoproteome of Kidney Cancer*") is a phosphoproteomics study comparing kidney cancer tissue and adjacent healthy tissue, identifying 8,962 proteins (6,415 phosphoproteins) and 44,728 phosphosites (10,266 previously unreported), and verifying some "missing proteins" under the Chromosome-Centric Human Proteome Project¹⁹⁸.

For the use-case session, we made use of the **dataset specification table**¹⁹⁹. This consists of the **sample metadata** submitted to the PRIDE database according to the Sample and Data Relationship Format for Proteomics²⁰⁰ (SDRF). **SDRF is part of the metadata standards** adopted by PRIDE / ProteomeXchange / Proteomics Standards Initiative²⁰¹ (PSI), used to encode sample-level metadata (e.g. biological sample type, condition, replicate, tissue, disease), and to link each sample to its corresponding datafile(s).

In PRIDE's record for a given dataset (such as [PXD006482](#)), there is a metadata table titled "Experimental Design (Samples)"; what the user submits via SDRF becomes or fills this table in the PRIDE web interface. That is, this table in GitHub is what was submitted (or what could be submitted) to supply PRIDE with structured information for that Experimental Design table.

Using the example, the working group engaged in a discussion on how to model the dataset, which included:

- **RAW files**. Instrument-generated proprietary format files (e.g., Thermo RAW files).
- **SEARCH files**. Results from peptide identification software (e.g., [Mascot](#)^{202,203} [.dat](#)²⁰⁴).

¹⁹⁶ <https://docs.google.com/document/d/1i7AUR2qL5PrgbSy0yndCISbYJT-XyfWi-XJmQJ0AEik>

¹⁹⁷ <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/pride/archive/projects/PXD006482>

¹⁹⁸ <https://hupo.org/c-hpp>

¹⁹⁹

<https://github.com/bigbio/proteomics-sample-metadata/blob/master/sdrf-specification-examples/PXD006482/PXD006482.sdrf.tsv#L13>

²⁰⁰ <https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.4a8cd2>

²⁰¹ <https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.9f60e7>

²⁰² <https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.8e1ce0>

²⁰³ <https://www.matrixscience.com>

²⁰⁴ <https://pnnl-comp-mass-spec.github.io/Uniprot-DAT-File-Parser/>

- **RESULT files.** Standard identification/quantification output in formats like `mzIdentML`^{205,206} and `mzTab`^{207,208} (required for complete submissions).
- **PEAK files.** Peak lists (e.g., Mascot `.mgf`).
- **FASTA files.** Protein sequence databases used during analysis (optional).

7.5.3.1. Key session outcomes

The EGA v2 model was able to capture the detailed processes involved in capturing a Proteomics experiment.

- **"Submission Type" distinction.** The long-standing division between "complete" and "partial" proteomics submissions is outdated. Most submissions are currently "partial" but, in reality, they contain all relevant data — the current issue is only about file standardization. Consensus: treat all submissions equally as full submissions; both partial and complete submissions require raw (experiment) and analysis files.
- **Core file types clarified. Experiment files** = raw data (from instruments); **Analysis files** = both `SEARCH` (software output) and `RESULT` (standardized, if available). **Recommendation:** always require both `SEARCH` and `RESULT` when possible, but accept non-standard formats too. Extra files (`FASTA`, spectrum libraries, etc.) remain optional.
- **Standardization and conversion.** Archives (like PRIDE) do not perform conversions themselves. They accept original software outputs, but for complete submissions they require results in supported standard formats. For FEGA, a stricter approach is recommended: always require `RESULT` files to ensure usability and reproducibility.
- **Sample metadata as a requirement.** Strong recommendation that SDRF files (sample metadata spreadsheets) be made mandatory in FEGA submissions. This ensures clinical and experimental context (e.g., sample sex, condition) is always captured — a gap in many PRIDE submissions.
- **Affinity proteomics (Olink²⁰⁹) emerges as a priority.** New technology (antibody-based, Next Generation Sequencing (NGS)-driven, high-throughput, cheap, plasma-based, clinically relevant). Olink data are usually released without raw NGS data (to avoid IP risks), only processed protein quantification + Quality Control (QC) metadata are released. Since FEGA deals with clinical/sensitive data, preparing for Olink submissions (including potential controlled-access) is essential.
- **Metadata modelling and provenance.** Importance of capturing clear relationships between samples, protocols, files, and outputs (including replicates, fractions, and processing steps). Flexibility is needed: not all users will provide detailed process chains, but the model should allow representation of complex workflows.

²⁰⁵ <https://www.psidev.info/mzidentml>

²⁰⁶ <https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.11889>

²⁰⁷ <https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.c12tyk>

²⁰⁸ <https://hupo-psi.github.io/mzTab/>

²⁰⁹ <https://olink.com/>

- **Ontology use and factor values.** Controlled vocabularies/ontologies (e.g., EFO, UBERON) are needed for consistency. The "factor value" concept (variables actually studied, e.g., tumour vs. normal) should be emphasised to help users and align with ISA/SDRF standards.

7.5.3.2. Worked example

Below, we represent the **proteomics dataset PXD006482** using the **EGA v2 model** (see [Figure 15](#)).

Given the inherent complexity and size (192 Samples) of this proteomics dataset, we have chosen to model only a subset of entities for this exercise, focusing primarily on those most relevant to illustrating the mapping process. As a result, not all entity types—particularly those related to administrative metadata (e.g., Studies)—are fully covered.

During the workshop, we also showcased how the EGA v2 metadata model can be used to represent **intermediate analytical processes** that are not currently supported by the EGA v1 model. Specifically, we defined a structured collection of protocols covering key experimental stages such as **protein quantification** and **differential expression analysis**. These protocol entities can be associated with multiple samples and are capable of producing distinct outputs depending on the inputs, thereby supporting a more granular and reusable representation of the experimental workflow.

In [Figure 15](#), we demonstrate a submission of a proteomics dataset in the EGA v2 model. Note the explicit representation of proteomics submission types via different file categories (RAW, SEARCH, RESULT).

Figure 15. Proteomics use case representation in EGA v2 model.

7.5.4. Microbiome

For the microbiome use case ([Annex 4](#)), we piloted FEQA pre-deposition and deposition workflows for microbiome studies (shotgun metagenomics, metatranscriptomics, metabolomics), discussed how **microbiome sample and study metadata** map into the EGA v2 metadata model, and refined it based on the FEQA Microbiome use-case session²¹⁰

²¹⁰ <https://docs.google.com/document/u/0/d/1uJdtTvDo3j8luaMKSdqX1GY7hhrj21J-4h2Qy6U9g1w>

(2025-07-01), including decisions about public archive deposition, decontamination, and metadata mapping.

7.5.4.1. Key session outcomes

Challenges and considerations:

- **Privacy/sensitivity:** although most microbiome chunks are non-identifiable after decontamination, procedures developed for European contexts/conditions on microbiome sensitivity should be surveyed and followed²¹¹.
- **Standardisation:** ensure other metadata standards and the EGA v2 model fields overlap cleanly; session feedback and the worked example informed improvements to EGA v2 model compatibility. Examples of these standards are the Environment Ontology^{212,213} (ENVO), NCBI Taxonomy²¹⁴, Minimum Information about any (x) Sequence^{215,216} (MIXS), Ontology for Biomedical Investigations^{217,218} (OBI).
- **Interoperability:** linkage patterns between public archives (e.g., ENA) and FEGA records must be explicit and machine-readable.

Conclusion and recommendations:

- **Default path:** decontaminate → deposit raw/processed sequences to ENA → submit metadata to FEGA following the EGA v2 model, ensuring linkage with ENA accessions.
- **Governance:** commission a short review to determine any Europe-level consensus/guidance on microbiome data sensitivity and consent languages.

7.5.4.2. Worked example

Below is a short, focused representation of the **stool-microbiome pipeline** as shown in the diagram ([Figure 16](#)), following the EGA v2 model. Because the diagram contains many elements, we model only the entities required to show the main provenance chain: how samples and protocols produce files and how those files assemble into three governed datasets. This multiple dataset governance, all under the same DAC, represents the scenario where a submission would not be distributed as a single unit, but follow different policies depending on the content of the linked data files.

It is important to note that, in the **absence of the sensitivity review**, multiple entities modelled in [Figure 16](#) could be removed from the FEGA submission. In other words, Datasets 1 and 2 of the figure may not contain sensitive data and, therefore, be suited for

²¹¹ Rodriguez, J., Cordaillat-Simmons, M., Badalato, N., Berger, B., Breton, H., de Lahondès, R., ... & Druart, C. (2024). Microbiome testing in Europe: navigating analytical, ethical and regulatory challenges. *Microbiome*, 12(1), 258.

²¹² <https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.azqskx>

²¹³ <https://jbiomedsem.biomedcentral.com/articles/10.1186/2041-1480-4-43>

²¹⁴ <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/taxonomy>

²¹⁵ <https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.9aa0zp>

²¹⁶ <https://w3id.org/mixs>

²¹⁷ <https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.284e1z>

²¹⁸ <https://github.com/obi-ontology/obi>

public archives such as the ENA. If that were the case, the FEQA submission would only encompass entities related to Dataset 3, which would certainly contain sensitive data. We included all datasets in the figure to satisfy the goal of this session: to assess whether the microbiome submission could be structured following the EGA v2 model. With this, we know that the most complex scenario (i.e., all datasets containing sensitive data) is covered and thus properly represented.

Data Description

- **Raw sequencing reads:** shotgun metagenomics FASTQ (after host-depletion where applicable).
- **Processed outputs:** CSV or TSV formats, taxonomic assignments, functional profiles, HMP Unified Metabolic Analysis Network²¹⁹ (HUMAN) outputs, pathway abundances.
- **Metadata:** Full MIxS-compatible sample metadata (sample type e.g., stool/biopsy, collection protocol, host phenotype, environmental parameters), plus study-level metadata per the EGA v2 model.
- **Storage/deposit recommendation:** Non-identifiable sequencing data should be deposited to public archives (e.g., ENA at EBI) and the FEQA submission should link to those accession(s). Human-sensitive or identifiable metadata should remain in FEQA access-controlled repositories.

Minimal metadata checklist

- **Project metadata:** title, description, submitter, keywords, publications.
- **Sample metadata:** sample name/ID, body site, collection method, host details (age, sex, health), environment.
- **Technical metadata:** sequencing platform, library prep, file names, run info.
- **Raw data:** FASTQ files (host-depleted where applicable).
- **Processed results:** taxonomic/functional profiles (.tsv/.csv).
- **Ethical compliance:** anonymisation, informed consent, ethics approval.

Processing / Methods

1. **Sampling:** sample (e.g., stool) collection and preparation.
2. **Sequencing:** DNA extraction, library preparation and sequencing.
3. **Preprocessing & QC:** adapter trimming, quality filtering.

²¹⁹ <https://doi.org/10.7554/eLife.65088>

4. **Host decontamination:** strict removal of human reads using well-documented pipelines^{220,221}. Participants in the use-case session mentioned decontamination as standard practice; human-derived reads typically are removed before public deposition.
5. **Taxonomic and functional profiling:** bioBakery3²²² tools such as MetaPhlan²²³, HUMAnN for shotgun metagenomics.
6. **Metadata mapping:** map sample and study metadata into the EGA v2 model (use other metadata/ontologies to complement the model).
7. **Deposition and linking:** deposit non-sensitive sequence files to ENA (or equivalent public archive) and include those accessions in FEPA submission metadata; deposit processed tables and reproducible workflows into FEPA as appropriate.

²²⁰ <https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC12018304/#TB1>

²²¹ Sirasani, J. P., Gardner, C., Jung, G., Lee, H., & Ahn, T. H. (2025). Bioinformatic approaches to blood and tissue microbiome analyses: challenges and perspectives. *Briefings in Bioinformatics*, 26(2), bbaf176.

²²² Beghini, F., McIver, L. J., Blanco-Míguez, A., Dubois, L., Asnicar, F., Maharjan, S., ... & Segata, N. (2021). Integrating taxonomic, functional, and strain-level profiling of diverse microbial communities with bioBakery 3. *elife*, 10, e65088.

²²³ <https://huttenhower.sph.harvard.edu/metaphlan/>

Figure 16. Diagram of a stool-microbiome research data lifecycle into the EGA v2 Metadata Model. Datasets 1 & 2 may fit best in public archives (e.g., ENA), simplifying the example.

7.6. Linked data

The introduction of **linked data principles** represents a significant step forward in the EGA v2 metadata model. It will be a valuable concept to accommodate, among others, multi-omics datasets. By **embedding contexts** (`@context`) in JSON Schemas, we ensure:

- Properties in schemas are resolvable to meaningful identifiers (e.g., `https://schema.org/name` for `name`).
- JSON documents referencing (in their `@context`) these schema files can be automatically expanded into RDF-compliant JSON-LD (see [Figure 17](#)) by inheriting the schemas' `@context`.

For instance, a `cohort.json` referencing `FEGA.cohort.json` through its URI²²⁴ will inherit the schema's context when expanded by a JSON-LD processor (see [Figure 17](#)). This enables terms used as keys (e.g., `'label'`) and CURIE values (e.g., `'ega:EGAD0000000001'`), to be expanded, pointing to resolvable URIs (e.g., `https://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#label` and `https://identifiers.org/ega:EGAD0000000001`, respectively).

Figure 17. Diagram depicting the expansion of a JSON document into JSON-LD with the addition of `@context`.

224

<https://raw.githubusercontent.com/M-casado/ega-metadata-schema/main/schemas/FEGA.cohort.json>

7.6.1. Benefits of Linked data

With the expansion of plain strings into fully resolvable URIs:

- Identifiers in the metadata become dereferenceable on the Web, letting clients **follow links directly to the defining vocabulary term or record**. This removes ambiguity and supports automatic link-traversal between archives.
- Because JSON-LD expansion yields standard IRIs, the **same document can be ingested by any RDF toolchain or SPARQL federation layer** without extra mapping. Essentially, unlocking cross-format and potentially cross-dataset querying and reasoning out-of-the-box.
- **Persistent identifiers** are one of the **keys to the FAIR principles**. This expansion boosts Findability and Interoperability scores for every record.
- Search engines prioritise JSON-LD for structured data. This translates into an **improved indexing and surfacing of FEGA content in domain-specific portals** (e.g., Google Dataset Search²²⁵) by embedding the expanded JSON-LD in each record. EGA already implements this context in a limited fashion for datasets alone (see [Figure 18](#)).
- Remote-context reuse means submitters need to **write less boilerplate to achieve a better semantic level** (i.e., lower verbosity with better semantic precision). This reduces maintenance overhead while following current best-practice guidance from W3C²²⁶.
- Resolvable URIs **let validation tools check not only syntax but also term existence** (e.g., "*does EGAD00000000001 exist or is it just a string?*") and **vocabulary consistency**.
- The same mechanism aligns seamlessly with **FAIR Data Point profiles** and **DCAT catalogues**, allowing each FEGA node to expose its holdings through standard discovery interfaces without duplicating information.

Formatting FEGA metadata in compliance with linked data also enables, with small tweaks to the FEGA websites, users to retrieve the metadata in different formats (e.g., JSON-LD, turtle, RDF...) directly from the portals.

These linked data capabilities have been tested for internal use-cases but are yet to be integrated with external archives (i.e., cross-archive semantic querying). This external capability may not be in scope for the EGA v2 model until the foundations are set.

²²⁵ <https://datasetsearch.research.google.com/>

²²⁶ <https://w3c.github.io/json-ld-bp/>

Figure 18. Representation of existing embedded contexts and how it improves the findability of EGA records on the web. (1) Record of a dataset in the EGA portal; (2) `application/ld+json` node embedded in the HTML of the record, containing context and metadata in JSON-LD format; (3) result of a query at Google Datasets²²⁷, returning the EGA dataset thanks to its embedded context.

7.6.2. Drawbacks of Linked data

Although linked data is the clear trend for archives to expose and link records, we consider not only their advantages but also their possible drawbacks.

It is worth noting that the use of linked data was designed to mainly add functionalities, but it introduces new dependencies and operational steps to maintain these features. Were linked data a failure in the FEQA metadata space, it would limit what the EGA v2 model could additionally do, but would not remove existing EGA v1 model features.

- Extra **processing steps** (e.g., expansion, flattening, framing) are needed to keep JSON Schema validation strict while allowing RDF-style flexibility. This would increase the difficulty in debugging and maintenance. Find more details in the [Framing](#) section.
- Greater reliance on networked resolution services:
 - Remote `@context` **dependencies can break JSON-LD expansion/framing** if the context URL is unavailable, rate-limited, or changes unexpectedly. This imposes a major dependency on GitHub to keep these contexts available;

²²⁷

<https://datasetsearch.research.google.com/search?src=0&query=sequencing%20cancer%20human&docid=L2cvMTFqY2p2X3Mzdw%3D%3D>

similar to the dependency of JSON Schemas being referenced and fetched from the same repository.

- Resolver downtime or slowness can directly break or hamper identifier validation and linked-data dereferencing.
- Increased governance burden: **stable namespaces** (e.g., `fega` namespace in `identifiers.org`) must be created and maintained long-term, to avoid semantic drift.
- Higher operational complexity for nodes: to be robust against external outages, nodes may need **local copies of contexts/schemas**.
- Skills and tooling overhead: supporting **RDF-native use** (e.g., SPARQL toolchains) can require specialist expertise.
- **Portal/API work increases**: serving multiple serialisations typically requires changes in FEGA portals (e.g., format negotiation).
- **Privacy/inference risk can increase**: linked, traversable metadata makes it easier to combine public crumbs with external sources, so the public/private split and controlled-access enforcement must be clear and carefully audited.
- **Strategic lock-in**: once downstream consumers rely on FEGA contexts, CURIE patterns, and dereferenceable identifiers, reverting to a "no-linked-data" posture becomes disruptive. In essence, offering new features to take them back later on may undermine reputation and trust in EGA.

7.7. Sensitive metadata

The EGA presents unique challenges as it is specifically tailored for human-derived data. Human omics data demands **meticulous handling to ensure compliance with national and international regulations, safeguarding data protection and privacy**. The following classification can be defined for this purpose:

- Risk is reduced by **publishing pseudonymised open-access metadata** (e.g., `biologicalSex` has value 'male'), linked to controlled-access records (e.g., encrypted `.json` phenopackets file) through EGA identifiers (e.g., `EGAN00000000001`).
- Directly **identifying metadata** (e.g., subject's names or addresses) must never be submitted as open-access metadata.
- Potentially **sensitive metadata** (e.g., subject's disease history) should be **open-access only where the submitter explicitly submits it as such**. Note that, if not as open-access, the submitter also has the option to submit metadata as controlled-access, encrypted, datafiles.

In essence, the access method proposal is to:

- Publicly disclose the **non-identifying submission metadata** required for findability and reuse (e.g., biological sex), as **pseudonymised metadata** compliant with the EGA v2 model. These are the metadata that the submitter explicitly provides as open-access.

- Enforce **controlled-access on submitted files**. These files are the (meta)data that the submitter explicitly provides as controlled-access. It is expected to include:
 - All information that the submitter deems **sensitive and identifiable personal data**. For example, a detailed phenopackets or electronic health record.
 - Any **other data** that the submitter wants to make accessible only through controlled authorisation. For example, non-identifiable personal data (e.g., subject's age) that could be aggregated with other publicly available datasets (e.g., lab results available at other archives) and become identifiable.

This submission routing (see [Figure 19](#)) enables submitters to propose²²⁸ **what metadata can be disclosed** (provided as open-access metadata) beyond the minimum EGA requirements **and what needs to be behind controlled-access** (provided as encrypted datafiles).

Figure 19. Summary diagram representing the submission proposal with regards to open and controlled access metadata.

An important distinction is that **controlled-access/open-access metadata do not always overlap with sensitive/non-sensitive**. The definition of special category (i.e., sensitive) personal data as per the General Data Protection Regulation²²⁹ (GDPR) does not impose *open-access* (i.e., publicly displayed) or *controlled-access* constraints. Instead, it simply requires a special level of protection for this type of personal data. Depending on the idiosyncrasies of each submission (e.g., other linked submissions, public records, journal articles), the **threshold for what level of exposure of open-access metadata may lead to re-identification of subjects varies**. With this approach, we give submitters the freedom to set this boundary themselves, to enable FAIR, yet privacy-preserving, submissions to FEQA.

²²⁸ In case that the data controller and submitter roles are not taken by the same legal entity: under GDPR the data controller remains responsible and makes the ultimate decision.

²²⁹ <https://gdpr-info.eu/issues/personal-data/>

Here, we propose a FEAGA-wide policy on how to handle open- and controlled-access submission metadata, promoting the responsible use of human-derived data by providing a **clear separation** between controlled-access and open-access submission metadata.

Furthermore, the EGA v2 model improves the **linkage between phenoclinical data and individuals**. With the current EGA v1 model, clinical metadata were poorly represented as generic *phenotype* analyses. In contrast, the EGA v2 model provides a better representation, enabling clinical data (e.g., phenopacket files, spreadsheets, CSV files) to be distributed easily through a diverse variety of processes, but always properly linked to the source individual.

Nevertheless, this approach comes with its challenges and future refinements, such as:

- Defining the **minimum requirements** for public metadata, to enable discoverability of relevant datasets without constraining the freedom of data submitters to set the access boundary of their submissions.
- Harmonising more than seventeen years of EGA submissions, where policy regarding open- and controlled-access may have been absent or vary.
- Introducing methods as opt-in options to enable **discoverability through controlled-access** data. For example, querying genomic variants through Beacon-v2, or displaying privacy-preserving ranges (e.g., age groups).

7.8. Improvements

As introduced in the [EGA v2 metadata model](#), the EGA v2 entails both conceptual and technology stack changes. In this section, we briefly go through the main improvements of both. The EGA v2 model shifts from a flat, submission-centric XML mindset to a graph-ready, JSON-LD framework that is resolvable on the Web, easily validated through open-source tools and flexible enough to represent future complex submissions.

7.8.1. Linked-data foundation

Through this model, FEAGA can serialise every record as JSON-LD, **allowing machines to traverse the metadata** as linked data across domains. Linked data practices directly support the **FAIR goals of findability and interoperability** that FEAGA advocates for.

In comparison, the EGA v1 model has poor linkage with external resources, as it lacks linked data approaches. Despite the fact that there are some properties whose purpose is to link records to a limited set of external resources (e.g., `XREF_LINK`), these are underutilised and most of the time missing in both programmatic and manual submissions. Efforts, such as comprehensive training materials, will be undertaken along EGA v2 model development to help submitters provide higher quality metadata and avoid underusing its features.

See further details in the [Linked Data](#) section.

7.8.2. Resolvable identifiers and external vocabularies

The schema requires CURIEs or HTTP URIs that resolve through identifiers.org or equivalent services, turning previously free-text fields into links that machines can dereference. For example, "biosample:SAMEA2397676" is resolved to "https://www.ebi.ac.uk/biosamples/samples/SAMEA2397676" in an automatic way.

Furthermore, we make use of **Biovalidator's custom keywords** that enable the JSON schema to connect to third party services (e.g., OLS, ENA, identifiers.org) during validation. For example, `isValidIdentifier`²³⁰ checks links across resources, catching typos before ingestion. Following the same example as above, if a user provided an ID "biosample:SAREEA2397676" (notice the typo, *R* instead of *M*), this error would be picked at validation and corrected by the submitter.

Likewise, ontology terms are validated with the OLS through Biovalidator's custom keyword `graphRestriction`²³¹, ensuring semantic consistency. For example, we can automatically check if "operon identification design" (EFO:0001785²³²) is a valid "study design" (EFO:0001426²³³) by relying on the JSON Schemas and Biovalidator to make the term comparison (i.e. 'is EFO:0001785 a child term of EFO:0001426?') through the OLS API.

In the current EGA v1 model, these constraints are non-existent, or depend on extensive Controlled Vocabularies (CV) that have to be individually maintained by the EGA. In contrast, relying on external resources simplifies the work of maintainers and keeps incoming submissions aligned with the latest field standards.

7.8.3. Wider scientific scope

New entity sets and controlled-vocabulary hooks let FEQA properly represent **use-cases** that were previously overlooked. For example, proteomics, microbiome, or array formats.

Furthermore, the **process-based approach** of the EGA v2 model enables a future-proof representation of incoming new use-cases without major schema rewrites.

7.8.4. Explicit, directional relationships

In the EGA v2 model, entities connect through typed edges, like `prov:wasDerivedFrom` or `schema:sameAs`. These **RDF relationships** are composed of three elements in sequence: subject-predicate-target. For example, we can encode that a biomaterial in FEQA (subject) is the same as (predicate) a sample in dbGap (target).

Each edge records its **direction**, mirroring graph-database conventions and avoiding ambiguous cross-references. This enables the exploration of semantic relationships in submissions, properly representing both simple and complex scenarios in a machine-readable way.

²³⁰ <https://github.com/elixir-europe/biovalidator?tab=readme-ov-file#isvalididentifier>

²³¹ <https://github.com/elixir-europe/biovalidator?tab=readme-ov-file#graphrestriction>

²³² http://www.ebi.ac.uk/efo/EFO_0001785

²³³ http://www.ebi.ac.uk/efo/EFO_0001426

7.8.5. Robust validation pipeline

A single CLI or REST call to Biovalidator **validates structure and semantics** (e.g., ontology terms) against the **same versioned JSON Schemas** wherever it runs, giving **reproducible results** in CI and production.

Biovalidator has been tested locally²³⁴ and through a public API endpoint²³⁵, obtaining stable results in terms of scalability and validation times. Furthermore, parallelization of validation requests can easily be configured by deploying multiple servers of Biovalidator.

7.8.6. Anticipated FAIR gains with the EGA v2 model

Adopting the FEQA JSON-LD-enabled schema is expected to measurably raise FAIR scores across all four principle groups (see [Table 3](#)).

Table 3. Anticipated FAIR gains of the EGA v2 model over the EGA v1 model.

FAIR aspect	Where we improve	Expected impact
Findable	Global, version-stable id IRIs and context-rich JSON-LD embedded in landing pages.	Search engines and tools such as FAIR-Checker ²³⁶ can resolve and index records automatically.
Accessible	HTTPS-resolvable identifiers and content-negotiation ²³⁷ for JSON-LD/RDF, not just for datasets.	Machines retrieve the same metadata humans see, improving automation.
Interoperable	Ontology-backed value sets and cross-entity links expressed as IRIs.	Schemas expand cleanly to RDF, enabling semantic queries (e.g., SPARQL) and automated cross-repository alignments
Reusable	Rich provenance (PROV-O), explicit licences and versioned release manifest.	Easier interpretation of the provenance of model entities and, therefore, of (meta)data.

7.8.7. Support input files

Procedural steps commonly require **datafiles as inputs**. For example, the Array Design Format (ADF) or the probe design of a microarray experiment, or the parameters file of a computational analysis.

²³⁴

https://github.com/EbiEga/ega-metadata-schema/tree/main/docs/biovalidator_benchmarks/2023.01.26_benchmarks/local_endpoint

²³⁵

https://github.com/EbiEga/ega-metadata-schema/tree/main/docs/biovalidator_benchmarks/2023.01.26_benchmarks/EGAs_endpoint

²³⁶ Gaignard, A., Rosnet, T., De Lamotte, F., Lefort, V., & Devignes, M. D. (2023). FAIR-Checker: supporting digital resource findability and reuse with Knowledge Graphs and Semantic Web standards. *Journal of Biomedical Semantics*, 14(1), 7.

²³⁷ Content-negotiation in RDF is an HTTP mechanism that serves different serialized formats (e.g., Turtle, JSON-LD, RDF/XML) of the same semantic resource from a single URL.

As of now, this dependency in the EGA v1 model cannot be represented, since EGA has uniquely stored the result files of an experiment or analysis. This leads to data requestors not being able to fully scrutinize and reproduce some of these processes.

In contrast, the **EGA v2 model enables representing these dependencies between processes and their inputs** beyond a biomaterial level, adequately representing datafile dependencies for each process (see examples in [Figure 12](#)).

7.9. Model versioning

As introduced in the [Metadata model naming conventions](#) section, there are two elements that need to be clearly understood: the core model and its extensions. These are versioned separately, maintaining, nonetheless, a hierarchy of the former over the latter.

For example, in [Figure 20](#) we see a made-up scenario, where FEQA Norway started their model extension (e.g., forking the `feqa-metadata-schema` repository) using EGA `v2.1.0`. This extension had some changes added, to cater for the node's needs (e.g., new property for a model entity), creating their extension `v1.0.0`. The core EGA model evolved independently at `feqa-metadata-schema`, reaching a new version `2.1.1`. At one point, FEQA Norway decided their extension (`v1.0.0`) could be merged with the source one, creating EGA `v2.2.0`. This is, nonetheless, a frictionless and oversimplified example. In reality, this process may take long periods of time, and efforts in resolving conflicts between the two parallel versions, depending on the diligence of their maintainers.

Figure 20. Made-up example of the core EGA v2 model and a FEQA Norway extension evolving over time.

7.9.1. EGA v2 model schemas

The EGA v2 model schemas follow a **branch** → **release-branch** → **tag** workflow:

- Day-to-day work lives on `dev`.
- The latest stable snapshot is `main`.

- Each published version first gets a branch following semantic version²³⁸ (vX.Y.Z), and later an immutable tag with the same name (vX.Y.Z). Validators and applications can fetch these static releases from GitHub through their version names.

Full details of the release process can be found at the [releases/README.md](#)²³⁹. The workflow includes **manual and automated steps**, where artifacts (e.g., [release_manifest.json](#)) are created, and semantic versions are checked, as well as the URIs used to identify each schema and its versions.

The [release_manifest.json](#)²⁴⁰ is a machine-readable summary of the schema version in each release. This document gets automatically generated prior to each release.

7.9.2. Model extensions

Extensions are copies of the main EGA v2 model schemas that are versioned independently yet maintain a hierarchical dependency with the original model. For example, in [Figure 20](#), FEGA Norway extension v1.0.0 is expected to be compatible with EGA v2.1.0.

These extensions have a different governance model (i.e., different ownership), and can be created by any institution or individual, as the project is open-source. They can also be merged with the core model at [fega-metadata-schema](#) following the contributing documentation²⁴¹.

7.10. Mapping archived data to the proposed model

7.10.1. Starting point

The **EGA has been live for more than 17 years**. We have archived more than **12,000 datasets**, and **millions of entities like Samples and Runs**²⁴². These were submitted following the EGA v1 model, which was based on ENA's object types and identifiers.

On top of these submissions following the EGA v1 model, another **~1,700 Array-based format (AF) datasets** have been archived. AF datasets use a bespoke method of submission as of now, in the absence of the EGA v2 metadata model.

7.10.2. Mapping strategy

In order to **bridge the gap** between models and to aid with the implementation of the EGA v2 model, we propose the creation of a **mapper library** (see [Table 4](#)). It is important to note that:

- Although **full automation** is the ultimate goal, the process may require human intervention to fully map some datasets. A classical example of this would be the

²³⁸ <https://semver.org>

²³⁹ <https://github.com/M-casado/fega-metadata-schema/blob/main/docs/releases/README.md>

²⁴⁰

https://github.com/M-casado/fega-metadata-schema/blob/main/docs/releases/release_manifest.json

²⁴¹ <https://github.com/M-casado/fega-metadata-schema/blob/main/CONTRIBUTING.md>

²⁴² <https://ega-archive.org/about/statistics/growth/>

Array Format (AF) metadata, which is processed in a different way to the rest of EGA-archived metadata.

- There will be **gaps when transforming metadata** from one to another. That is unavoidable, by definition, when a more detailed model is to be adopted. This will require lowering standards during the conversion, or enhancing existing data by making assumptions. For example:
 - If a user provided 'M' as the value for `sex` in their EGA v1 model submission, we would assume that it's referring to 'male' in the `sex` attribute of the EGA v2 model.
 - If an analysis in the EGA v1 model has multiple sample references, and multiple output files, the sample-file cardinality is not explicit. This changes in the EGA v2 model, and would require a fine-tuned process, for example matching sample identification (i.e. aliases or `subject_id`) with filenames.

For further details about the comparison between these two models, refer to the [CEGA use-case](#) section.

Clues for the semantic equivalence (e.g., a `sample` in EGA v1 model is equivalent to a `biomaterial` in the v2 one) can be found within the EGA v2 model JSON Schemas following the Simple Standard for Sharing Ontological Mappings²⁴³ (SSSOM) specification. This would be of great help to the automatic conversion across models, by semantically bridging entities on both ends of the transformation.

Table 4. EGA v1-v2 models mapping strategy overview.

Task	Mechanism	Notes
Schema-to-schema links	Each FEQA JSON Schema property embeds, where applicable, a <code>meta:sssomMappings</code> that points to the semantic equivalent in the EGA v1 model (among others).	Machine-readable, versioned with the codebase.
Entity transformation	An "EGA v1-v2" mapper library would aid with the automatic conversion between EGA v1 and v2 models.	Handles 1-to-many splits (e.g., EGA v1 <code>Experiment</code> becomes <code>protocolCollection</code> + <code>Process</code>).
Semantic enrichment	When the source (following the EGA v1 model) contains fields with known identifiers as free-text, the mapper library would expand them as CURIEs; ontological gaps are flagged for manual review.	Ensures every core node has a dereferenceable <code>id</code> .

²⁴³ <https://mapping-commons.github.io/sssom>

7.11. Implementation plan

The **implementation** of the EGA v2 model involves a key step in archiving by CEGA and any FEGA node: **validation against the EGA v2 model JSON Schemas**. Regardless of the method of submission (e.g., GUI, APIs) and storage (e.g., Postgres, MongoDB), as long as the metadata submitted are validated against the EGA v2 model and communicated across nodes in a compatible format, implementation is considered to be achieved.

1. **Phase 0.** Preparation.
 - a. Publish **EGA v2 JSON Schemas**, creating the first stable release of the model.
 - b. Develop the **EGA v1-v2 mapper** and start testing model transformations.
2. **Phase 1.** CEGA pilot.
 - a. **Dual ingestion:** new submissions at EBI flow through both validators: EGA v1 model at CEGA/FEGA (for *status quo*) and EGA v2 model (for early adopters).
 - b. **Back-fill:** progressively convert historical records.
 - c. **API shim:** deploy the mapper as a lightweight REST service that translates EGA v1-v2 payloads back-to-back so external services that still rely on EGA v1 can continue unmodified.
3. **Phase 2.** Federation preview.
 - a. **Engage FEGA nodes** with the improvements of the EGA v2 model.
 - i. Create and provide **training** to early adopter nodes, external services and end-users that would like to adopt the EGA v2 model.
 - ii. Run **cross-node FAIR dashboards** to demonstrate the quality gains of adopting the model (see [Model Improvements](#) section).
4. **Phase 3.** Progressive adoption.
 - a. **Opt-in migration:** nodes progressively include a metadata validation step against the EGA v2 model in their primary submission methods.
 - b. **Deprecation notice.** After the majority of the FEGA nodes migrate, EGA v1 model schema updates become security-only, and a deprecation plan is put in place.
5. **Phase 4.** Consolidation.
 - a. EGA v1 model is **frozen**, while the mapper is retained as a long-term support utility. All new submissions to FEGA are validated against the EGA v2 model.

8. Governance

All schemas, examples and tests live in the **public feqa-metadata-schema repository** under the MIT licence²⁴⁴, and every pull request triggers the same validation matrix the archive runs in production.

Releases will be **documented** in GitHub and Zenodo, enabling history tracking of the model evolution at any time.

The FEQA network will manage the EGA v2 metadata model through a three-tier structure that mirrors the wider FEQA organisational layout²⁴⁵ (see [Table 5](#)).

Table 5. FEQA governing groups over the EGA v2 model.

Name	Role for the model	Composition
Strategic Committee	Endorses every <i>major</i> model release (v2.0.0, v3.0.0, etc.) or can exercise a 30-day veto if concerns arise	Senior FEQA representatives from all operational nodes
Operations Committee	Reviews implementation impact, schedules deployment windows, and triggers the veto timer once a release candidate is tabled	Technical leads and product owners from operational nodes
Metadata Working Group (MWG)	Drafts changes, triages change requests, resolves issues, and reviews pull requests	Volunteer modellers from the majority of FEQA nodes (both onboarding and operational). Potentially invited experts.

8.1. Change release flow

Continuous development is the norm for the FEQA metadata schemas: routine improvements move through the repository like any other open-source project. When an urgent fix or a formally versioned release is required, the steps in [Table 6](#), and the minimum notice they impose, ensure every node can react in time and the governance bodies can intervene if necessary.

This change release flow, like most of the work in this report, is but a **proposal**, still to be validated by all participating drivers (FEQA nodes, CEQA, and respective committees). Once the EGA v2 model is released and this approach is tested, it will be updated accordingly.

²⁴⁴ <https://github.com/EGA-archive/feqa-metadata-schema/blob/main/LICENSE>

²⁴⁵ <https://docs.google.com/document/d/1jHyj85iOr7gl75VmHX3DjVI4E-USWSD8d9HG1Z-f4SM>

Table 6. Change release flow step-by-step.

Phase	Drivers	Minimum notice / deadline*
1 Change request logged (issue / PR)	Any node / stakeholder	None
2 Triage and label (patch / minor / major / emergency)	Metadata Working Group (MWG)	≤ 1 week
3 Escalation to Operations Committee (in case of emergency / major)	Metadata Working Group (MWG)	≤ 2 days
4 Operations Committee review (impact on node software and workflows)	Operations Committee	15 days (Emergency) / 30 days (Major)
5 Strategic Committee veto window (for major)	Strategic reps	+ 15 days
6 PR with changes and human check	Metadata Working Group (MWG)	≤ 1 week after veto period, depending on severity
7 Trigger release vX.Y.Z	Metadata Working Group (MWG)	Immediately after changes are reviewed
8 Create tag vX.Y.Z + GitHub Release	Metadata Working Group (MWG)	As needed following the release process.

*Longer consultation is welcome when time allows. These figures are the minimum periods to be enforced when a fix is blocking validation or roll-out.

8.2. Accountability and transparency

- **Authorship:** A markdown file `AUTHORS.md`²⁴⁶ at the root of feqa-metadata-schema lists, for each contributor, their basic details and contributions. Furthermore, a `CODEOWNERS`²⁴⁷ file helps trace relevant people whose reviews gatekeep specific changes to the repository.
- **Contacts:** each operational node designates at least one MWG contact. MWG members are listed along with their roles and contact details in the `AUTHORS.md` file.

²⁴⁶ <https://github.com/M-casado/feqa-metadata-schema/blob/main/AUTHORS.md>

²⁴⁷ <https://github.com/M-casado/feqa-metadata-schema/blob/main/.github/CODEOWNERS>

- **Public log:** the `CHANGELOG` and `release_manifest.json` for every tag lets anyone trace exactly which schema changed in which release. This fulfils FAIR provenance recommendations.

8.3. Alignment with the FEQA change-management plan

The plan's **Emergency / Major / Minor / Patch** categories map directly onto the semantic versioning bump and review windows above:

- Minor and Patch changes remain within MWG autonomy.
- Major changes invoke the committee veto cycle.
- Emergency patches (e.g. security, legal compliance) bypass the timer but must be back-ported to `main` and `dev` within 48 hours, with a retrospective review by the Strategic and Operations committees, as per the FEQA change-management policy (v1.0, 03-10-2024)²⁴⁸.

Further operational details (diagrams, CI scripts, release checklists...) live in the `releases/README.md` of the schema repository and are kept up to date by the MWG team.

9. Dependencies

Here we list **external dependencies** of the EGA v2 model, which both enhance and constrain the technical approach. They let us reuse community infrastructure for identifiers, ontologies, and standards, while keeping the FEQA schemas lightweight and interoperable.

For what mitigation measures are in place for each dependency, refer to the [Risks and mitigation](#) section.

9.1. Validation services

- **ELIXIR Biovalidator**²⁴⁹. Core JSON Schema validator with ontology and taxonomy checks; runs as CLI or server. Our schemas and CI depend on it.
- **Ontology Lookup Service (OLS4) API**²⁵⁰. Used by Biovalidator's custom keywords such as `graphRestriction`, `isValidTerm`, and `isChildTermOf`. If unavailable, semantic checks in validation cannot run.
- **Identifiers.org**²⁵¹ **registry and resolver**. Backing `isValidIdentifier` and CURIE/IRI resolution.

²⁴⁸

https://docs.google.com/document/d/1xSzh38zMxINBIN9aHQ6_Z5sacE1clmRBtkbSi5x_qZ4/edit?tab=t.0#heading=h.bly7duplwf9t

²⁴⁹ <https://github.com/elixir-europe/biovalidator>

²⁵⁰ <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ols4/help>

²⁵¹ identifiers.org

- **ENA Taxonomy services**²⁵². Potential use for `isValidTaxonomy` checks supported by Biovalidator.

9.2. Upstream schemas and profiles

- **GA4GH Beacon v2**²⁵³. Selected JSON Schemas (e.g., Cohort's `defaultSchema.json`²⁵⁴) are reused to stay aligned with Beacon models and formats.
- **BioSchemas**²⁵⁵. Profiles and generated JSON Schema/JSON-LD assets inform parts of our model (e.g., `ComputationalWorkflow` profile²⁵⁶).
- **ISA-JSON**²⁵⁷. ISA model schemas and specs (e.g., `process_parameter_value_schema.json`²⁵⁸) are a reference for possible reuse of concepts and fields.
- **DCAT**²⁵⁹. Schemas and specs are a reference for possible reuse of concepts and fields.
- **DCAT-AP**²⁶⁰. DCAT application profile for data portals in Europe, describing catalogues, datasets and data services.
- **HealthDCAT-AP**²⁶¹. HealthDCAT Application Profile is a domain-specific (health data) metadata model designed to support the implementation of the secondary use framework under the European Health Data Space (EHDS).
- **JSON-LD**²⁶². Base JSON-LD structure schema (`jsonld-schema.json`²⁶³) taken and referenced in the FEGA schemas.

Some of these are added to the FEGA repository as static files, while others are forked and referenced. See [Risks and Mitigation](#) for further details.

9.3. Hosting and resolution

- **GitHub**²⁶⁴. Schemas are distributed via repository URLs and fetched in validation through `raw.githubusercontent.com`; outages or rate limits can affect remote resolution.

²⁵² <https://ena-docs.readthedocs.io/en/latest/retrieval/programmatic-access/taxon-api.html?>

²⁵³ <https://github.com/ga4gh-beacon/beacon-v2>

²⁵⁴

<https://github.com/ga4gh-beacon/beacon-v2/blob/main/models/json/beacon-v2-default-model/cohorts/defaultSchema.json>

²⁵⁵ <https://bioschemas.org/>

²⁵⁶ <https://bioschemas.org/profiles/ComputationalWorkflow/1.0-RELEASE>

²⁵⁷ <https://isa-specs.readthedocs.io/en/latest/isajson.html?>

²⁵⁸ <https://isa-specs.readthedocs.io/en/latest/isajson.html#process-parameter-value-schema-json>

²⁵⁹ <https://www.w3.org/TR/vocab-dcat/>

²⁶⁰ <https://semiceu.github.io/DCAT-AP/releases/3.0.1/>

²⁶¹ <https://healthdataeu.pages.code.europa.eu/healthdcat-ap/releases/release-6>

²⁶² <https://github.com/json-ld/json-ld.org>

²⁶³ <https://github.com/json-ld/json-ld.org/blob/main/schemas/jsonld-schema.json>

²⁶⁴ <https://github.com/>

9.4. Linked data processing

- **JSON-LD processors.** When remote contexts are used, processors retrieve them per the JSON-LD 1.1 API, so availability of those context URLs matters.

10. Risks and mitigation

Table 7. Risks and mitigations overview.

Dependency	Service	Risk	Mitigation
Validation services	ELIXIR Biovalidator	Bug or breaking change blocks validation pipeline.	Pin versions in CI, keep a vetted fork, add regression tests, and contribute fixes upstream.
		Upstream custom keywords change behaviour (e.g., <code>graphRestriction</code>).	
		Speed of validation becoming a bottleneck.	Base speed tested in validation benchmarks ²⁶⁵ (2023); run yearly benchmarks to assess performance with more intensive tests.
	Reliance on internet connection for integrated API checks (e.g., OLS, <code>identifiers.org</code>).	For ontology checks (e.g., <code>graphRestriction</code>), use local static OWL files representing ontologies, which can then be connected to Biovalidator (as a local OLS API) with a slight technical overhead.	
	OLS4 API	API outage or latency prevents ontology checks.	Stop validation service to prevent misvalidated submissions; if OLS4 is slow to come back online, consider a local OLS deployment backed by OWL files.

²⁶⁵

https://github.com/EbiEga/ega-metadata-schema/tree/main/docs/biovalidator_benchmarks/2023.01.26_benchmarks/local_endpoint#json-validation-summary

Dependency	Service	Risk	Mitigation
		Backwards-incompatible API: impossibility of validating terms in older ontology versions. For example, if a term X was valid for ontology Y v1, but changed in v2, OLS4 API will not enable us to check years later if X was valid with Y v1.	Always validate against the latest version of ontologies. When metadata are validated and ingested by a FEQA node, it's assumed they were valid against the latest version at the time. For backwards-compatible validation (i.e., older versions), we may: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Validate against local OWL API with versions. Release ontology-free schemas for older versions, enabling validation of syntax but not semantics.
	Identifiers.org	Registry updates change prefix targets (e.g., biosample:... → biosamples:...).	Identifiers.org handles <i>deactivated</i> entries, and redirects properly to the new active ones.
		Resolver downtime breaks CURIE/IRI validation and redirects.	Stop validation service to prevent misvalidated submissions. Alternatively, remove <code>isValidIdentifier</code> and <code>isValidTaxonomy</code> from the schemas.
	ENA Taxonomy	API unavailable hampers <code>isValidTaxonomy</code> checks.	
Upstream schemas and profiles	GA4GH Beacon v2	Upstream schema changes or repo restructure break our references.	Beacon v2 references are not directly to the root Beacon v2 repository, but to a fork of it instead (for now at M-casado ²⁶⁶). Therefore, control over new changes is in FEQA's hands. If references are swapped to the root beacon v2 repo, and this risk triggers, fallback is to have references to versioned Beacon v2 releases (e.g., v2.2.0 ²⁶⁷).
	BioSchemas	Spec evolution diverges from our reuse.	Adapt FEQA repo's local copy of spec (i.e., schemas) to new standards, and only release new changes when stable for FEQA.
	DCAT		
	DCAT-AP		
	HealthDCAT-AP		
	ISA-JSON		

²⁶⁶ <https://github.com/M-casado/beacon-v2>

²⁶⁷ <https://github.com/ga4gh-beacon/beacon-v2/tree/v2.2.0>

Dependency	Service	Risk	Mitigation
	JSON-LD	Remote context URLs unavailable during expansion or framing.	Bundle local copies of contexts, prefer content-negotiated URLs we control (i.e., the ones in the FEGA repo).
Hosting and resolution	GitHub	GitHub outage or raw resolution rate limits block \$id/\$ref fetches.	Use cached schemas in existing Biovalidator instances; deploy validator instances with <i>local</i> schemas instead of letting it fetch them when referenced.
	FEGA nodes	FEGA nodes have specific needs for validation.	FEGA nodes can deploy multiple local instances of the validator; and can fork the FEGA schema repo and alter it as needed. Responsibility for compliance would lie with the node maintainer.

11. Results

The FEGA MWG has successfully developed an **abstract metadata model for the FEGA** network, along with its **proposed technical stack**, that significantly advances FAIR principles and enables linked data interoperability. The following summarises key advancements and collaborative outcomes:

- **First abstract metadata model version drafted:** a process-oriented and ontology-aligned metadata model was drafted, shifting from traditional biology-centric schemata to a flexible, procedural framework suitable for diverse life science domains.
- **Ongoing model coverage:** the model consists of entities and their attributes. These are being standardised using JSON Schemas with JSON-LD contexts in the group's GitHub repository²⁶⁸.
- **Ontology and linked data integration:** the model incorporates widely adopted ontologies and vocabularies (e.g., EFO, DCAT), ensuring interoperability through linked data standards.
- **Community-driven use-case validation:** usage scenarios across genomics, proteomics, microarrays, and microbiomes have been modeled in dedicated FEGA use-case sessions. These sessions have demonstrated that the new model accommodates a variety of submission types and experimental designs. See further details in the [Use-cases](#) section.

²⁶⁸ <https://github.com/M-casado/feqa-metadata-schema/tree/main/schemas>

- **Governance and versioning:** transparent governance and an open development process determine the model's continuous evolution. Robust versioning practices and collaborative mechanisms ensure traceability and reproducibility.
- **Community engagement:** a diverse group of stakeholders was consulted and involved in the design, development and testing of each component, from the abstract model to the JSON Schemas.

12. Discussion

12.1. FEGA operational structure

FEGA faces a complex data landscape with different regulatory, technical, and scientific requirements. This report documents monthly cross-node meetings and international workshops that focused on identifying the pain points with the EGA v1 model. Mainly, the (i) inability to model non-genomics data, (ii) limited ability to represent common procedural steps and (iii) reliance on controlled vocabularies and free-text fields.

The FEGA MWG responded by shifting the core modelling focus from the prevailing experiment/analysis paradigm to a **process-oriented, modular framework**. This decision—rooted in the lessons of the Human Cell Atlas and SEEK models—was not driven by abstraction, but by the practical need to represent workflows from genomics and beyond, such as imaging, microarray, microbiome, and proteomics.

12.2. Community-rooted model design and use-case validation

A defining characteristic of the process was deliberate, open engagement with FEGA nodes and external partners from the very beginning (see [Group Formation](#) section).

Furthermore, the FEGA use-case sessions were not isolated workshops, but recurring, hands-on collaborations. Each session dissected real or synthetic datasets, actively shaping the entity structure and model granularity. The flexibility with which the model accommodated diverse use-cases—illustrated with side-by-side diagrams and worked mappings—proved instrumental in building confidence and fostering consensus, especially for data types (e.g., proteomics) that were not previously well-supported.

12.3. Ontology integration and linked-data adoption

Instead of relying on static, locally maintained controlled vocabularies, the model uses standardized ontologies through CURIEs and URIs, ensuring (1) alignment with field standards, and (2) syntactic validation plus selected semantic checks (e.g., ontology term validation). Linked data principles are embedded by default, making the EGA v2 metadata model suitable for federated search and semantic querying in the future.

Nevertheless, the use of external ontologies comes with its own challenges, such as dependency on ontology updates, and the risk of "ontology drift". The MWG will address these challenges through automated tooling and continuous monitoring. This makes the

model not only machine-readable and interoperable, but also prepared for future expansion within biomedical data ecosystems.

12.4. Evaluation and impact

As of now, national FEGA nodes struggle to balance between remaining consistent with the EGA v1 model and creating their own metadata models or bespoke solutions that cater to their needs. This commonly results in duplicated effort or loss of metadata fidelity across nodes.

The EGA v2 model aims to overcome that challenge by becoming the common FEGA standard for metadata validation. This is supported through **open-source software and tooling**, which will aid cross-node communication and reduce both ambiguity and manual curation overhead.

Trust from the scientific community is backed by transparency in governance (e.g., clear release/versioning pathways, public logs) and direct representation of participant feedback in schema evolution.

12.5. Challenges

- **Ontology change management:** dependency on external vocabularies mandates further automation and community alerting as terms evolve.
- **Granularity negotiation:** user story analysis exposed the problem between minimal submitter burden and the need for detailed provenance. In other words, how much information and flexibility is *enough* for a data requester without overwhelming the submitter.
- **ELSI differences across nodes:** different countries have different rules for consent and data sharing. This caused some friction during federation. A future solution involves adding **machine-readable consent codes** to ensure that automated systems respect legal boundaries.

See specific challenges in the [Open questions](#) section.

13. Next steps

- Finalising JSON Schemas, including **ontology mappings** and **validation constraints**.
- **Continuous development** in the GH repository. Including JSON Schemas, housekeeping scripts, GH actions and overall documentation.
- **Community engagement** through (1) further use-case sessions (e.g., Biobanks, Imaging, Cohorts) and (2) **external stakeholder feedback** (e.g., GDI, ELIXIR, GA4GH).

- **Widening adoption and interoperability** by developing semi-automated mapper libraries (e.g., EGA v1-v2 models) to assist smooth migration of legacy records and implementation of the EGA v2 model.
- **Expanding linked data capabilities** to enable semantic queries and interoperability testing. For example, adding comprehensive `@context` to every schema and, potentially, adding RDF dumps and a public SPARQL endpoint.
- Designing and creating the `fega` namespace in `identifiers.org` and ensuring its resolvability. Further FEGA-wide discussions on the matter of PIDs are required.
- **Dissemination** of the work done by the MWG, including adding remarks in public aggregators of documentation like RDMkit, FAIRsharing, etc.
- Further overlap with the **HealthDCAT-AP** standard. This would include not only mapping entities from both models, but directly reusing/adapting existing validation constraints for HealthDCAT-AP:
 - Validation through SHACL shapes for DCAT-overlapping entities (e.g., Dataset).
 - Support for CEGA/FEGA metadata to be harvested by portals like `data.europa.eu`²⁶⁹.
- Testing and adopting a **Metadata Quality Assessment (MQA)** system for submissions, similar to: (1) `data.europa.eu`'s MQA²⁷⁰, or (2) Quantum²⁷¹ (HealthData@EU data quality label project).
- Collaborate with the **ELIXIR FHDPortal**²⁷² on how to reconcile the portal's drafted JSON Schemas²⁷³ and the future EGA v2 model JSON Schemas.
- Collaborate with the **German Human Genome-Phenome Archive**²⁷⁴ (GHGA), Germany's FEGA node, to reconcile its JSON Schemas²⁷⁵ with the future EGA v2 model JSON Schemas.
- Define a **FEGA-wide default policy for open- vs controlled-access metadata** exposure (minimum public metadata, review responsibilities, and enforcement).

²⁶⁹ <https://data.europa.eu>

²⁷⁰ <https://data.europa.eu/mqa/methodology>

²⁷¹ <https://www.healthinformationportal.eu/services/data-quality>

²⁷²

<https://elixir-europe.org/how-we-work/scientific-programme/commissioned-services/science/hdtr/fhd>

²⁷³ <https://github.com/sib-swiss/fhdportal-cli/tree/main/config/schemas>

²⁷⁴ <https://www.ghga.de/>

²⁷⁵ <https://github.com/ghga-de/ghga-metadata-schema>

14. Open questions

Table 8. Open questions of the Technical Report.

Question	Comment
<i>Should we use SHACL shapes instead of JSON Schemas for semantic validation, like other profiles (e.g., DCAT-US 3.0²⁷⁶)?</i>	Given that (1) Biovalidator accepts JSON Schema as input and (2) JSON-LD is an RDF-friendly format for semantic data, we advocate for keeping JSON Schema as the current validation constraint language. In the long-term, FEAGA may release additional SHACL shapes for graph-level validation, or shift to SHACL validation altogether. Thanks to JSON-LD being an RDF format with <code>@context</code> , the transition, if it were to occur, to SHACL would be relatively straightforward.
<i>Should we promote Beacon-v2 to create its own @context?</i>	As of now, their JSON Schemas lack <code>@context</code> , and instead we are the ones adding it in our entities that use Beacon-v2 schemas.
<i>Should we add more entities (e.g., Genomic Variations) from other standards and models? Are they needed by FEAGA?</i>	There is a sweet spot between trying to model <i>everything</i> in life, and modelling not enough. The usefulness towards the goals of the model (findability, analysis, reproducibility...) would be considered.
<i>How should we handle dependencies on other standards?</i>	As of now, we are directly referencing, for example, Beacon-v2 JSON Schemas in their repositories (M-casado's fork ²⁷⁷ for compatibility). This opens the possibility of changes done in other repositories affecting integrity within the FEAGA schemas. An alternative is to store these references as static files within the repo prior to each release.
<i>How should we handle dependencies on ontologies?</i>	Controlled vocabulary terms within ontologies, like EFO, HPO or Mondo, are embedded in the JSON Schemas. This facilitates validation, but obfuscates traceability of validation when ontologies evolve over time. This could be alleviated, a priori, by freezing external resources and releasing them along the JSON Schemas.
<i>What other standards should we reuse directly?</i>	This involves standards that are not simply taken for inspiration (e.g., DCAT-AP), but instead are directly embedded in the EGA v2 model (e.g., Beacon-v2). Possibilities include Beacon-v2, JSON-LD, BioSchemas, ISA-JSON, DCAT, and GDI HDM.
<i>How to reconcile a FEAGA node's relational storage database with a graph-based procedural model?</i>	Although the EGA v2 model is not tied to the possible implementations of it by the nodes, it would be naive to disjoin both. Thus, some trade-offs are already agreed within the model to limit the number of combinations and possible complexity of process trees that could be represented by it. For example, by using the <i>Protocol Collection</i> entity, or by creating additional "checklists" (e.g., 'if your protocol is X, I'm expecting Y and Z as an input') to impose limitations for submitters.

²⁷⁶ <https://doi-do.github.io/dcat-us/#profile-validation>

²⁷⁷ <https://github.com/M-casado/beacon-v2/tree/biovalidator-test>

Question	Comment
<p><i>Should Datafiles be a dcat:Dataset instead of a dcat:Distribution?</i></p>	<p>Following a strict DCAT definition, multiple dcat:Distribution of a dataset are intended to be used as different methods to access the <u>same</u> information. Albeit explained in the Dataset and Datafiles section, our definition of Datafiles would fall better under a dcat:Dataset of one single file, which would be a "part" of a bigger dcat:Dataset that corresponds to the common (F)EGA Dataset. The former, with one single file, would then have multiple possible dcat:Distribution(s) itself. These additional steps may overcomplicate the model, though, but would be more conformant with the DCAT specification.</p>
<p><i>Should we add prov:Association linking the prov:Activity and the prov:Plan?</i></p>	<p>In the PROV-O specification, a prov:hadPlan is not intended to be used directly on a prov:Activity. Instead, its domain is prov:Association. In the EGA v2 model, we are skipping this middle step, linking prov:Activity and prov:Plan directly through a prov:hadPlan, when the most strict linkage would be: prov:Activity –prov:qualifiedAssociation→ prov:Association –prov:hadPlan→ prov:Plan. Similar to other open questions, we consider these trade-offs of the models in order to simplify the model and reduce the query joins and steps to retrieve metadata.</p>
<p><i>Is protocol ordering relevant for FEGA submissions?</i></p>	<p>The relationship prov:hadMember expresses membership alone, not ordering. Since the main aim of the model is not to contain the full and detailed protocol information of each activity, but the information to enable discoverability of data, protocol order was not deemed worth bringing into the mix. If a more detailed view of the protocols used for each activity is needed, other models such as P-Plan could be considered.</p>
<p><i>Should the linkage between Protocol and Process be exclusively through a Protocol Collection?</i></p>	<p>If we are strict with the representation aspect, having both Process–ProtocolCollection and Process–Protocol make sense. Nevertheless, we need a balance between (1) being semantically sound, (2) having extra steps in between (i.e., the Protocol Collection) that would hinder queries to retrieve data, and (3) the complexity for submitters/users to understand that a Process may be linked to a Protocol in two different ways. For that reason, we assume the default linkage would be through Protocol Collections, but a direct, inferred, relationship between Process and Protocol could be made at the implementation level (see Figure 5).</p>

15. Annexes

Number	Name
1	"CEGA Use-case - post-session modelling results.svg" ²⁷⁸
2	"Microarray Use-case - post-session modelling results.svg" ²⁷⁹
3	"Proteomics Use-case - post-session modelling results.svg" ²⁸⁰
4	"Microbiome Use-case - post-session modelling results.svg" ²⁸¹

²⁷⁸ <https://drive.google.com/file/d/1vR7dJGQuyaV1rf1XbSfdyRRKJbQCYzJy>

²⁷⁹ https://drive.google.com/file/d/1RnMw7R4eDRuo4mXnoFShCclf_WlJ0m81

²⁸⁰ <https://drive.google.com/file/d/1qUrfKkzegLciolPSHuYyAarrWgpNs3QV>

²⁸¹ <https://drive.google.com/file/d/1oNkau8mvMILOf0Kus4pNt1AnsvIEbHue>